

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

IMMERSE D3.4_V1

IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D 3.4

Analysis reports after carrying out the
research across countries in schools
and other learning environments

VERSION 1.0

Contract No: 822536

Summary

This report presents the results of the large-scale cross-country survey on refugee and migrant children's integration conducted as part of the Horizon 2020 research project Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant Children in Europe (IMMERSE). The purpose of IMMERSE is to examine the socio-educational integration of refugee and migrant children in schools and other educational environments, formal and non-formal, in their host countries across Europe.

Authors

Various

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822536

Deliverable Nr.	D3.4	Work Package Nr.	WP3	Task/s Nr.	T3.3, T3.4
Work Package Title	Data collection and monitoring				
Linked Task/s Title	T3.3 Data Collection & T3.4 Data Analysis				
Status	Final	(Draft/Draft Final/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	(PU-Public, PP, RE-Restricted, CO-Confidential)			
Due date deliverable	M53	Submission date	17.10.2023		
Deliverable version	V1				

Approval status			
FUNCTION	NAME	DATE	SIGNATURE
Deliverable responsible	UCC		
WP leader	UCC		
Project coordinator	Comillas		

Document Contributors

Contributors	Organization	Reviewers	Organization
Dr Shirley Martin	UCC		
Dr Reana Maier	UCC		
Dr Jacqui O’Riordan	UCC		
Dr Deirdre Horgan	UCC		
Dr Inma Serrano	COM		
MSc Eva Bajo Marcos	COM		
MSc Elena Rodríguez Ventosa Herrera	COM		
Dr Ángela Ordoñez Carabaño	COM		

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
1	17.10.2023	

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	1
2	Introduction	2
3	Overview of formal school environments in the six IMMERSE partner countries	3
3.1	<i>Education Systems in Participating IMMERSE Countries</i>	3
4	Overview of the quantitative methodology	6
4.1	<i>Child and Youth Engagement and Co-creation in Immerse Quantitative Methodology Design and Analysis</i>	6
4.2	<i>IMMERSE survey questionnaires</i>	8
4.3	<i>IMMERSE Survey Sampling</i>	9
5	Description of the obtained sample	14
6	Results of Quantitative Data	23
6.1	<i>INTEGRATION RESULTS</i>	27
6.1.1	<i>LANGUAGE AND CULTURE DIMENSION</i>	27
6.1.2	<i>WELL-BEING DIMENSION</i>	30
6.1.3	<i>SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS DIMENSION</i>	32
6.2	<i>BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS</i>	39
6.2.1	<i>SCHOOL ORGANISATION AND TEACHERS CLUSTER</i>	39
6.2.2	<i>MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES CLUSTER</i>	43
6.2.3	<i>NEGATIVE ATTITUDES</i>	44
6.2.4	<i>LEARNING SUPPORT CLUSTER</i>	47
7	Conclusion	49
a.	<i>Reflections on methodological issues</i>	49
b.	<i>Conclusions on quantitative survey findings</i>	51
8	References	55
9	Appendices	58
a.	<i>Appendix A: IMMERSE questionnaires-</i>	58
b.	<i>Appendix B: Country sampling overviews and changes</i>	59
i.	<i>Belgium</i>	59
ii.	<i>Germany</i>	61
iii.	<i>Greece</i>	64
iv.	<i>Ireland</i>	67
v.	<i>Italy</i>	70
vi.	<i>Spain</i>	73

1 Executive Summary

This report presents the results of the large-scale cross-country survey on refugee and migrant children's integration conducted as part of the Horizon 2020 research project Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant Children in Europe (IMMERSE). The purpose of IMMERSE is to examine the socio-educational integration of refugee and migrant children in schools and other educational environments, formal and non-formal, in their host countries across Europe. Because the primary goal of IMMERSE was to form policy recommendations at European and national levels to facilitate the socio-educational integration of refugee and migrant children, we required a substantial evidence base drawn from the lived experiences of children in which to ground those recommendation. While the project pursued multiple strategies to build the evidence base, primary data collection using questionnaires was the cornerstone of the project. The data collection was conducted in Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain between June 2021 and June 2023, across a total of 406 sites with over 24,000 children, almost 60% of whom are from a refugee or migrant background.

The quantitative results from IMMERSE depict a multifaceted view of the integration experiences of children with migrant backgrounds in Europe. These findings span several dimensions of integration, encompassing language and culture, indicators of well-being, social connectedness, and factors influencing integration, such as school organization, access to mental health services, learning support, and experiences of negative attitudes towards them among migrant children.

Key findings from the survey include some positive findings on well-being indicators, with overall high levels of happiness reported by migrant and non-migrant children in the survey, as well as on indicators related to sense of belonging in school, participation in extra-curricular activities and access to learning and language support. However, the research also uncovers negative integration experiences and challenges faced by migrant-background children, including variations in their sense of belonging and instances of bullying and harassment.

The intersectionality of children's experiences is also very evident in the research. In several of the integration indicator's differences emerge in the data when considering first- and second-generation migrant children, with age and gender also emerging as key influential factors in the integration indicators results. The convergence of gender, age, and migration status represents a crucial factor, underscoring the importance of addressing these aspects when providing support

for the socio-educational integration of migrant children. Furthermore, significant variations exist among participating countries, underscoring the importance of considering national contexts in interpreting the results.

2 Introduction

This report presents the results of the quantitative data collection for WP3 of the IMMERSE project, which was conducted between June 2021 and June 2023 across a total of 406 sites with over 24,000 children, almost 60% (13,345) of whom are from a refugee or migrant background. The report presents the first overview of children's integration results and barriers and facilitators based on this large-scale cross-country survey data, which intends to provide a representative image of the national and Europe's reality on refugee and migrant children's integration by focusing on six countries (Belgium, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, and Spain) representing the diverse European migration contexts. Concurrently, educational contexts vary across the six countries (a summary is provided in Section 3 below), and children's migration status can intersect complexly with these educational pathways.

The survey questionnaires were specifically designed to capture data on the IMMERSE dashboard of indicators, a new set of indicators on children's integration results and barriers and facilitators that was co-created with children and stakeholders on the first year of the project (see Section 4). The questionnaires also capture other relevant variables and demographics to enable rich analysis of the dashboard indicators. The data collection was focused on schools across all six countries, in order to collect data not only from children (in primary and secondary school levels) but also at the level of school (from principals and teachers). This strategy was supplemented by the collection of data in other experiential environments, with the aim to reach out populations (such as unaccompanied children and asylum seekers) that might be more difficult to access in the formal school environments (D3.5. will focus on the results for these populations).

This large-scale cross-country survey data is unique and challenging. It involved creating questionnaires instruments to collect data from participants in diverse locations, who came from potentially hundreds of different origin countries, spoke multiple languages, and many of whom were in vulnerable or precarious conditions due to their migration status. Implementation in the field was aided by the development of a digital data collection system (with traditional pen-and-paper back-ups) that could bring together multiple strands of data into a central database for analysis and link to the Dashboard, but it coincided with the COVID-19 outbreak and other impactful

events such as the refugee crisis following the 2022 Ukraine crisis, which added to the challenges of collecting data on migrant children in an ever-changing socio-political scenario.

Section 3 provides an overview of formal school environments/system in the six IMMERSE countries.

Section 4 provides an overview of the methodology of the data collection. The section begins with a discussion on the co-creative and youth engagement elements that were central to the IMMERSE data collection and research design. It provides an overview of the sampling strategy, the recruitment of the research sample and the impact of Covid-19 on access to schools for data collection.

Section 5 presents the obtained sample results and introduces some considerations for the analysis.

Section 6 presents the results on IMMERSE indicators from the data collection.

Section 7 presents a discussion on the methodological issues and concluding comments on the IMMERSE survey results.

3 Overview of formal school environments in the six IMMERSE partner countries.

3.1 Education Systems in Participating IMMERSE Countries

The IMMERSE research partners represent diverse national school systems across six partner countries with unique histories and characteristics within each country and many region-specific characteristics. Notwithstanding this, there are also some commonalities within the education systems and the sample for the IMMERSE study, starting with a common European Framework of rights and all countries' alignment with the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED). The focus of IMMERSE is on compulsory school age and mainly encompasses ISCED levels 1-31. The age of compulsory formal school in each IMMERSE partner country varies slightly, with a common starting age of 6 across the partners (5 in the case of Greece) and an upper age of 15 in Greece, 16 years in Ireland, Greece, Italy and Spain, and 18 in Belgium and Germany (Eurydice 2022).²

¹ This broadly aligns to Primary Education or ISCED 1; Lower Secondary Education or ISCED 2 and Upper Secondary Education or ISCED 3.

² This limit is 19 in 5 German landers.

According to Eurydice, within the then 28-member European Union (EU-28)³, there are three main types of primary and secondary education systems: "single"; "common core" and "early tracking". Using this Eurydice classification all the IMMERSE partner countries, except for Germany, are categorised by Eurydice as being education systems with a 'common core curriculum'. The common core curriculum is 'characterized by a general education programme followed by all pupils, but unlike the single structure, this is provided in two separate institutions, one for primary and one for lower secondary education' (2019, p.12). Germany has an early tracking system, meaning that at the end of the four years of primary education, pupils are referred to ISCED 2 institutions which provide differentiated general education (ibid, p.12). This system leads to a much broader range of educational programmes available from ISCED 3 onwards.

Public funding for compulsory education is common across OECD countries, including IMMERSE partner countries (OECD 2023). This can be largely from central, regional or local government. Ireland, Greece and Italy to a lesser extent have high levels of central government funding, whereas regional and local government funding more common in Italy, Spain and Belgium (Atkinson et al. 2005). Christianity, deeply ingrained in Europe's cultural and ethical bedrock, has played a pivotal role in shaping the European states and their respective national education systems (Bedmar and Delgado-Cobano, 2014: 55). Within IMMERSE partner countries this continues to be most evident in Spain, Italy and Ireland where there has been historical and constitutional Catholic influence. Although diminishing and increasingly contested as these societies become more secular, there continues to be a predominantly Catholic influence in these countries school systems.

3.2 Migrant children in Education in IMMERSE partner countries.

Available data indicates the percentage of foreign-born and migrant heritage children as well their increasing numbers in education. For the IMMERSE Partner countries between 3-5% of their school-age population were foreign born (Eurostat 2018, see Figure 1). Both Germany and Spain, long-standing host countries, had the same percentage of foreign-born school aged children (5%), while Ireland, a more recent host country, had the lowest rate (3%). PISA 2018 results, provide data on the percentage of students (15-year-old) from immigrant backgrounds and the changes in this population from 2009 to 2018. Overall, there was an increase of 3% in the number of immigrant students across OECD countries. All IMMERSE partner countries experienced increases in the

³ This number includes the UK, a member state which has since exited the EU.

overall number of immigrant children during this period, with some differences in relation to first- and second-generation migrant children.

Figure 1 Foreign Born School Children in Partner Countries (PISA, 2018)

Recent increases in migrant and refugees have added considerably to the number of migrant children in schools in Europe, with a particular impact of the war in Ukraine. Since the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 almost 2 million Ukrainians have sought refuge in several European countries and it is argued that 'inclusion in national education systems becomes the most sustainable way for host governments to ensure access to quality education, promote social cohesion, and prepare Ukrainian students for the future' (UNESCO 2023:np). By 15th August 2023, the combined number of Ukrainian refugees recorded in IMMERSE partner countries reached 1,628,420, accounting for around 27.6% of the total number in Europe (UNESCO, 2023). According to UNESCO's estimates, 40% of Ukrainian refugees are children.

In all six IMMERSE participating countries, as dictated by EU Law (Article 14 (2) of the Reception Conditions Directive), migrant children of compulsory school age have the same rights and obligations to participate in education as those born in the host country (Noorani et al. 2019).

Nevertheless, issues continue to arise with regard to access, particularly for newly arrived migrant children (Massing et al, 2023, UNHRC, UNICEF, IOM 2019). Waiting times to access education, as well as different regional access policies have been identified by FRA (2019; 2020) as key challenges for access to education. The former is evident in Italy, and both are particularly evident in Greece. Intersections between accommodation provision and access to education also result in barriers faced by children in Germany (FRA 2020). In Italy there were concerns that schools were

reluctant to take children over 15 who did not speak Italian and these children then became the responsibility of the adult education system – CPIAs (Provincial Centres for Adult Instruction). In Germany delays in the assessment of migrant students' qualifications led to students being placed in incorrect levels of education and delay in school enrolment was identified as contributing to school drop-out (ibid). Access to education after compulsory school age, particularly for irregular migrants and asylum seekers, is problematic. In Belgium, some voluntary-oriented compensatory programmes require resident permits which may preclude certain migrant young people from participation (Noorani et al. 2019, p. 8). There is also evidence that migrant children, especially those who arrive after compulsory school age, may experience barriers accessing second level education (FRA 2019).

Challenges in providing education have also intensified since 2015 with the arrival of larger numbers of refugees and asylum seekers (Koehler and Schneider, 2019). For example, in May 2022 the EU reported that enrolment of Ukrainian children in their host countries varied widely by country. Only 9% of Ukrainian children were enrolled in schools in Greece, 39% in German, 54% in Belgium (no data available for the Flemish community), 71% in Italy, 75% in Spain and 92% in Ireland (Noorani & Antonello, 2022). Updated data on the enrolment is poor, with Ireland and Germany being the only IMMERSE countries providing recent figures. It was published that 213,556 Ukrainian children and young people were enrolled in German schools in mid-July of 2023, indicating that nearly all (97%) refugee children were receiving compulsory education (Brücker, et al., 2023). In Ireland, the data indicated that 88% of Ukrainian children aged 5-18 (15,625) had been enrolled in schools by the end of the 2022-2023 school year (Department of Education, 2023).

4 Overview of the quantitative methodology

4.1 Child and Youth Engagement and Co-creation in Immerse Quantitative Methodology Design and Analysis

Co-creation of research methodology and instruments

IMMERSE has applied a collaborative research process in which children and young people were partners and influencers in the research process (Landsdown, 2011). They were involved in co-creative activities which informed the research process including co-designing and validating the research methodology, influencing the data analysis and co-designing and contributing to dissemination activities. To ensure children's voices are incorporated throughout IMMERSE's

activities a Children and Young People's Advisory Group⁴ (CYPAG) was set up. The use of such advisory groups is central to grounding the research in children's experiences and adhering to the spirit of Article 12 of the UN Convention of the Rights of the Child. The CYPAG was formed and overseen by the University College Cork research team drawing on the team's extensive experience of working with children's advisory groups (Horgan and Martin, 2021). Recruited in conjunction with existing NGOs who interact with migrant children, this advisory group ran for the duration of the 5-year project with CYPAG meetings taking place twice annually. It was comprised of children of refugee and migrant backgrounds, aged between 9 and 16 years of age (at the outset of the project). The CYPAG were collaborators in the definition of the research framework, deciding on the issues and questions to be looked at and how to look at them and thus, shaped all subsequent activities, including data collection design and implementation. They have played a critical role in the construction of the children's questionnaires and in the piloting process. The incorporation of other children's voices, in addition to the CYPAG, was present at multiple points in the questionnaire construction process itself. Qualitative workshops with children during the first phase of IMMERSE helped to establish the foundations for the compilation of the Dashboard. Further qualitative workshops were held for children and young people to validate the Dashboard and the first draft of Dashboard questionnaire items. These sessions helped the researchers choose which items to include and discard, informed us as to where questions/answers were unclear or not relevant, and what gaps were present and assessed the age-appropriateness of the questionnaire. The questionnaires were piloted in school settings by the research teams, which confirmed that the youngest members of our participant cohort would need high levels of support and facilitation to complete their questionnaires, and it was decided at this point to exclude 6-year-olds. The feedback we received from these sources improved the data collection instruments' clarity and relevance and demonstrated the need for researcher facilitation with our youngest participants.

Children and young people's involvement in analysis

The CYPAG were heavily involved in the data analysis phase of the project. The UCC team developed capacity-building exercises on quantitative data analysis for the CYPAG which focused on what it means to analyse data and how to go about it. Working with the emerging data, the

⁴ Literature on CYPAG outlines the benefits of child and youth advisory groups, such as their contribution to specifying important topics for young people, sharing insights and experiences, providing advice to ensure effective methods, and identifying key findings, recommendations and policy priorities arising from the findings, as well as identifying means to disseminate (Jones et al., 2018; Moore et al., 2016; Oliveras et al., 2018; Moore et al., 2020).

CYPAG identified key variables and relationships which they would like to see in further data analysis including the influence of gender and country of origin on integration.⁵

4.2 IMMERSE survey questionnaires.

A suite of instruments was envisioned for data collection, the most important of which were the children's questionnaires, with parent, principal, and teacher questionnaires providing key information on children's backgrounds and school environment.⁶ The main phase of survey construction took approximately one year, overlapping with the finalisation of the dashboard (see D1.5), and it was finalised in the late third quarter of 2020.⁷ Selection of the non-dashboard contextual items was guided by established research literature on education and integration and qualitative results from IMMERSE WP1 (see IMMERSE Working Papers 1, 2, and 3), and building on other large-scale national and international surveys of children and young people (PISA, HBSC, TIMSS, Growing Up in Ireland).

Children's questionnaires

Creating questionnaires for children, particularly young children and children of refugee and migrant backgrounds, has unique challenges: age and level of cognitive development, appropriate question and answer types, use of visual aids, translation and cultural understanding, and the importance of pre-testing/piloting. To collect data from the full range of school-aged children, we designed two different instruments – one suitable for young children (7-9 years) and one suitable for older children (10-18 years).

The questionnaire for younger children was particularly challenging, as there are very few studies that collect data from children in this age range using questionnaires. The final instrument was shorter than the older children's questionnaire, focusing on selected dashboard indicator items and limiting contextual, non-dashboard items. It excluded any items and indicators that did not apply to younger children or were too abstract or complex for them to understand. It also used simpler language, limited basic question types/answer options, and included a series of bespoke cartoons to help evoke question meaning. The older children's questionnaire contains a wider range of non-

⁵ The role of the CYPAG is explored in more detail in Deliverable D5.6

⁶ The development of the suite of IMMERSE questionnaires is described in greater detail in Deliverable 3.1 and Maier, Martin, Horgan, and O'Riordan (forthcoming).

⁷ Small revisions continued until the start of primary data collection in June 2021.

dashboard items, more varied question types and answer options, a section on the impact of Covid-19 and did not include cartoons. Both instruments were conceived for children to complete online (CAPI), for which a specific IT solution was developed, but a paper-and-pencil (PAP) version was also developed and utilised.

Considerations of language, translation and different cultural understandings of concepts were critical elements of the construction process, and all the instruments were piloted and assessed with children of different origins in all six countries. The instruments were translated into the official languages of the consortium countries – Dutch, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, and Spanish – and into four additional languages identified by the partners as the most useful – Arabic, Farsi, Romanian, and Chinese. At a later stage translation were also developed to Urdu, Somali, Russian and Ukrainian. The translation process was revealing of some potential problems with clarity, intention, and understanding of certain concepts and resulted in further refinement of the instruments. The English language versions of the questionnaires are available at the IMMERSE data and document repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/immerse-h2020>

Adult questionnaires (parents, teachers, directors)

Parent, principal, and teacher questionnaires were also designed to provide key information on children's backgrounds and school environment, as well as meso-level dashboard indicators (such as supports for migrant students and inclusive education in the curriculum). The English language versions of these are also included in the following link. <https://zenodo.org/communities/immerse-h2020>

4.3. IMMERSE Survey Sampling

Common sampling framework

Data collection was conducted with a common sampling framework, which was then developed in each country to adapt to the specificities of each country's context and to difficulties and limitations emerging along the way.⁸ Decisions around sampling were guided by the WP leaders but were ultimately made by each research partner based on the country's context, available

⁸ The general approach to sampling and a detailed account of each country's specific sampling plan are described in *IMMERSE D3.1 Report on Standardisation across Data Collection and Implementation*.

information to be used as sample frames, and practical and logistical limitations, while taking into consideration overall methodological concerns.

Sample selection took place at regional, site, and classroom levels, accounting for critical axes of variability but also with the imperative of reaching predetermined targets of numbers of children of migrant background. This included focusing on regions (and then schools) with a significant presence of migrant school-age population. As a result, the sample predominantly focused on urban areas, as throughout Europe foreign-born populations are predominantly in urban and metropolitan regions, which is also true for the IMMERSE partner countries (Eurostat 2016) (See Appendix C for further details).

Selection of sites (primary sampling units)

Within the selected regions (see Appendix C for a whole listing), **formal educational sites** (schools) were selected using a stratified random sampling strategy, which was adjusted in each country to accommodate the different education systems and available information. When it came to adapting the framework to each of the partner countries, the variation found even within educational systems and the variation in the available data required to build a stratified random sampling pool were very significant challenges. The type and amount of data on individual schools was often incomplete or simply did not exist. Alternative school characteristics and proxy measures had to be investigated making the overall sampling approach less unified than initially expected. Foreseeing difficulties in some contexts to obtain the ambitious numerical target, non-probability sampling strategies were considered from the beginning as back-ups to help ensure this target. Due to the extensive and long-lasting impact of COVID-19 during the implementation of the survey (see more below), non-probability sampling strategies were finally introduced in all countries.

Private education institutions (including European or international schools) were not included in the sample (as they make up a very small proportion of schools and of migrant-background population in all IMMERSE countries). All partners similarly excluded special needs-focused schools because, as the project did not have the resources to adapt the data collection for their needs.

The sampling strategy also included **other “non-formal educational” sites** (such as receptions centres for refugees or unaccompanied minors), for which we employed convenience sampling (non-probability). The inclusion of these sites allowed for the incorporation of hard-to-reach migrant children, such as unaccompanied minors, or children who may be ‘in-transit’ or on the move

and staying in temporary accommodation or refugee camps in Greece or Italy. Research demonstrates that these children can be less likely to be accessing formal education and social services in the host country and are often hard-to-reach (Topalovic et al, 2021). Therefore, it would have been difficult to access these children through formal education setting. In addition, other non-formal education settings which work directly with migrant children (e.g., after-school groups, language programmes, summer schools) were included in the sampling strategy to ensure the inclusion of these hard-to-reach children and to maximize the heterogeneity of the resulting sample.

Selection of children at sites (final sampling units)

Although the sampling strategy focused refugee and migrant background children as a target, the sampling included children of all backgrounds present in the selected sites⁹. This was important from an ethical and practical point of view (so that no child would feel excluded, and that migrant children would not be singled out); and also from a methodological point of view (in order to be able to compare the results of non-migrant children to those of migrant children). This is also in line with the inclusive approach that frames the IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators. Against this background, the schools and centres were approached with a request for the participation of whole classes, full year groups or the whole school (depending on school characteristics and country-specific sampling strategies). Only classes in educational levels covering the intended age range (7-18 years) participated. This was nonetheless accommodated to each site's possibilities for participation, which sometimes meant collecting data from only certain classes, year groups or groups of students (see Annex C for country-specific details).

Finally, children's participation was fully voluntary. Research with children that respects them as active citizens and right-holders requires due attention to their capacity to make decisions for themselves (Lundy & McEvoy, 2012). Thus, it was of critical importance, both ethically and in the spirit of the project's commitment to children's voice and rights, for the children and young people themselves to make the ultimate decision regarding their participation. For this reason all children participating in the IMMERSE survey were asked for their assent to participate.¹⁰ However, in many

⁹ This inclusive class-room based approach also led to a small number of participants completing the questionnaire who were outside the age range of the survey (7-18 years).

¹⁰ The older children and younger children's questionnaires both started with an introductory section that outlined, in straightforward language (further simplified for the younger children), what they would be asked about and explained their rights in terms of data protection, privacy, anonymity, and refusal to participate or withdrawal at any time. This

cases we also needed to first seek consent for their participation from parents/guardians (or someone who could stand in place of parents/guardians). From a legal point of view there is country-to-country variation in the age threshold above which children can give consent on their own for their personal information to be stored/used (Milkaite & Lievens, 2019) – for instance, in Spain it is 14, while in Ireland it is 16. From a cultural and institutional point of view, acceptable approaches to seek parental (or guardian) consent also varied from country to country, and even region to region. These differing legal standards and institutional norms meant that some partners operated under quite restrictive consent procedures (therefore often gathering data from fewer students at each site) than other partners operating under less restrictive procedures (and therefore more likely to obtain more children’s participation at each site). The different existing approaches for parental consent are summarised in the table below.

Table 1. Consent approaches

Consent approach	Description
Participant own	Participant is legally allowed to consent to personal information being stored/used under GDPR and is considered old enough to consent to participate in social research under general ethical standards in their location
Parent/guardian – OPT IN	Participant cannot legally consent to personal information being stored/used under GDPR and/or is not considered old enough to consent to participate in social research according to general ethical stands in their location. Consent from parent or guardian is required. Parent/guardian must be provided with information on the study, and consent for child to participate must be explicitly given in written or digital form. Also known as active consent.
Parent/guardian – OPT OUT	Participant cannot legally consent to personal information being stored used under GDPR and/or is not considered old enough to consent to participate in social research according to general ethical stands in their location. Consent from parent or guardian is required. Parent/guardian must be provided with information on the study and given the opportunity to withhold consent for the child to participate. If consent is not explicitly denied, child can participate. Also known as passive consent.

written section was supplemented by verbal introductions and explanations if members of a research team were present for the data collection. The first question on the children’s questionnaires was whether they agreed to participate or not. Very few children exercised the option not to participate, but it was necessary that they be given the choice, with no ramifications for refusal or withdrawal.

School-based

Parents/guardians provide a blanket consent to the school at the beginning of the academic year for any school-related activities. This essentially allows the school to stand in place of the parent/guardian and provide consent for any particular activity. Consent for individual activities from parents/guardians is therefore not required.

Adults' participation

In formal sites (schools), principals and teachers were requested to fulfil separate surveys providing information on the school, and principals and teachers' background. This participation, as with children, was fully voluntary and not always fulfilled. Participation from parents encountered a double barrier, sometimes from schools (sometimes not willing to request this participation due to practical limitations and low levels of parental engagement) and most frequently from parents themselves, with an extremely low response rate. This was not entirely unexpected; parent involvement is often a stumbling block when doing research with children, and when the target population is a vulnerable population, like migrants, reluctance to participate can be exacerbated (Heiervang & Goodman, 2011). Following pilots, we attempted to develop strategies to help combat low response rates from parents, such as online information sessions for parents.¹¹ Despite the effort the teams put into collecting data from parents, none of the partners had a sufficiently high response rate to the parent questionnaire during main phase data collection to be able to use parent data in the final analysis (four out of six of the partners had less than 10% of children's questionnaires with an accompanying parent questionnaire). Therefore, these data are not analysed in this report.

Impact of COVID-19 and Ukrainian crisis

The sampling plans were constructed in the early phases of the Covid-19 pandemic and before the outbreak of the war in Ukraine and led to difficulties experienced by all partners in recruiting schools and scheduling data collection, particularly in-person site visits. In particular, the Covid-19 pandemic, associated lockdowns and restrictions on school activities/visitors to schools continues to have a very negative impact on the capacity of schools to engage in research and other non-core curricular activities. In Europe, many countries continued to experience multiple

¹¹ As a failsafe, we replicated some of the most critical questions from the parent questionnaire on the older children's questionnaires (namely, parent's country of birth and migration status), in case we were not successful in securing parent responses.

periods of either partial or complete school closure during 2020, 2021 and into 2022. Movement restrictions, both general restrictions on movement in local areas and restrictions on travel between different regions, impacted partner access to participant sites. Even when schools reopened for in-person learning, there were continued restrictions on visitors and educational interruptions arose from staff and student absences due to Covid-19 infection or being a close contact of someone with Covid and associated isolation periods. The outbreak of the war in Ukraine and the intake of large numbers of Ukrainian children to European schools, particularly in Germany, also impacted the ability of schools to engage in research. Due to these events, several adjustments had to be made to the original sampling plans. Most importantly, the data collection had to be delayed, and the two data collection windows originally designed (involving an interim analysis) were set aside in favour of an extended single data collection window from June 2021 to June 2023.

5 Description of the obtained sample

Participating sites

In total, **406 sites** participated in the survey, with the largest number of sites involved in Greece (148) and the lowest in Belgium (20). Over one fourth of these (106) were non-formal sites, aimed at capturing hard-to-reach and frequently underrepresented populations.¹²

¹² The number of non-formal sites was particularly large in Greece (41), Spain (31) and Italy (18).

Figure 2 Number of sites by country and type

The sites came from the regions selected in the original sampling design in all of the participating countries and from the additional regions eventually included in all six countries (see Appendix C for full listing). Considering only formal sites, these added regions are particularly significant in the German and Belgian samples (68% and 33%), while they represent a smaller percentage in Italy, Ireland and Spain (12-18%), and particularly in the Greek sample (4%). For non-formal sites, these additional regions were very significant for Spain (100%) and Italy (50%). The participating sites are largely **urban**, with a marginal representation (6%) of rural sites (which are totally absent in Italy and Germany). City environments dominate (77%) and are followed by towns and suburbs (16%). Non-formal sites have a similar urban-rural distribution, with a larger presence of rural environments (12%).

Figure 3 Regional Distribution of Formal Sites

Formal sites (i.e. schools, the main target of the survey) include primary-level schools and secondary-level schools (38% and 44%), and also schools that include both levels (13%). The latter are a feature of Spanish and Italian samples (where they represent 31% and 67% respectively). Almost half (47%) are fully **government funded**, and only 13% fall below a 75% of government funding, reflecting the dominant government funding model for education across OECD countries (OECD 2023). In all countries, the average share of government-funding per school is between 87-96%.¹³ All schools are **publicly-managed**, except in Spain and Ireland, where around 30% of schools in the sample are managed by a non-public entity. In these two countries, some sites also declare a religious affiliation (30% in Spain, 65% in Ireland).¹⁴ This is absent in Italy and marginal in Greece (2%).

Principal and teacher surveys were only collected in formal sites. Principals were the most difficult to obtain (in only 163 of these formal sites) as compared to teachers (209), and children (287). But there was significant variation across countries: the lowest participation rates of directors (principals) were registered in Germany (17% of formal sites participating) and Italy (32%), while in

¹³ Germany falls below this range. However, since this specific information on schools is provided by the principal's questionnaire, due to low participation in Germany and Belgium (n<15), the information available from these countries is not really reliable.

¹⁴ Also, Belgium (18%), but as noted, this information is not reliable.

the rest of countries this ranged from 60% (Greece) to 92% (Spain). For teachers, the participation rate went from 53% and 61% in Germany and Greece, respectively, to 90% in Spain. Among the sites collecting info on teachers, the number of participating teachers varied from 1 to 78. The average number of teachers participating per site went from 3 and 4 in Germany and Greece, respectively, to 16 and 17 in Italy and Spain. The average number of **children** participating in each site (formal or informal) was 62 overall and significantly differed by countries, from 47 and 54 in Ireland and Greece, to 106 in Italy and Spain. The number of children participating per site was overall much smaller in non-formal sites (average 15 vs 79).

Children’s sample

The **final sample of 24,419 children** is constituted by 6 national samples, whose sizes range between 1,272 (Belgium) and 8,194 children (Italy). Of these children, 1,785 (7%) participated in non-formal sites. This percentage is larger in the Greek and Belgian samples (14% and 10%). It is important to note that these **national samples** are sufficiently large to be indicative of each national context (and particularly of the selected regions), although additional statistical treatment is required to establish full statistical representativeness. The results’ analysis below is thus focused on the comparison across countries. Although we also present the results for the total sample, this is only descriptive of the obtained sample, but not representative of the six countries as a whole.

Figure 4 Number of children per country and type of site

These children come from the regions selected in the original sampling design and from the additional regions eventually included in all six countries (see Annex C for full listing). These added regions are particularly significant in the German sample (69%), and represent a noticeable percentage in Belgium (23%), Spain (18%), Italy (10%) and Ireland (7%), while it is marginal in Greece (1%). The resulting children's sample is also largely **urban** (only 2% were collected in rural sites): city environments predominate (84%) together with towns and suburbs (14%). Germany presents the highest percentage of town and suburbs environments (37%). This general distribution slightly changes in the subsample of children in non-formal sites, where the percentage of rural environments reaches 7% and city environments diminishes to 78%.

Figure 5 Distribution of Children per region in each country (all sites included)¹⁵

The majority of the sample (55%) is constituted by **migrant-background** children (13,344). Of these, 23% are migrants (5,623) and 32% are children born from migrant parents (7,721). The percentage of migrants varies significantly per country, from 13% in Italy to 48% in Germany. The percentage of children with migrant background is similar for all countries except Greece, where it reaches 41%. The remaining of the sample is constituted by children without migrant-background (39%) and by children who have not provided sufficient information to establish their migrant status (6%). The

¹⁵ The “other” regions category in each country represents the following: Wallonia (Belgium); Saxony-Anhalt, Baden-Württemberg and Saxony (Germany); Waterford (Ireland); Albacete, Lorca-Murcia, Lleida, Cuenca, Toledo, Cantabria, Balearic Islands, Salamanca) Seville, Cordoba, Almeria, Granada, Cadiz (Spain); Veneto, Bari, Prato and Scalea (Italy); Euboea, Achaia and Thrace (Greece)

latter will be excluded from the presentation of results below. This distribution significantly changes for non-formal sites, where the majority of sampled children are migrants (65%) or have migrant parents (21%). Only 10% are children without migrant-background and 4% do not provide sufficient information to assess their migrant status.

Figure 6 Number and Distribution of children sample by migrant status in each country (excluding children with undefined migrant status)

Figure 7 Distribution of children by migrant status in each country

The **age structure** of the sample is mostly composed by small children (6-10), early adolescents (11-13) and middle adolescents (14-16) representing 25%, 30% and 30% each. Late adolescents (17-18) represent 13% of the sample. Due to the inclusive approach adopted in the sampling strategy, 2% of the collected surveys correspond to ages between 19-22, which will be excluded from the results analysis presented below.¹⁶ Some variations exist per country, with smaller representations of small children in Belgium (11%), early adolescents in Germany (17%), middle adolescents in Ireland (18%), and late adolescents in Spain and Ireland (8%). The sample has a slightly larger representation of **boys (50%) than girls (46%)**, and it includes a small percentage of

¹⁶ A total of 18% of all these respondents answered the "younger children" questionnaire (13% in non-formal sites) and 82% answered the "older children" questionnaires (87% in non-formal sites).

children who define their gender "in another way" (1%) or who prefer not to answer (2%). Overall, there is only a significantly larger representation of males relative to females in particular among late adolescents (in Belgium, Greece, Spain and Ireland) (see Figure 8. below).

Figure 8 Age and gender distribution of children sample per country

6 Results of Quantitative Data

This section presents the first overview of **children’s integration results and barriers and facilitators** based on the IMMERSE survey results. The IMMERSE surveys were specifically designed to collect new data on children and schools that was required, and otherwise unavailable, for 16 indicators in the IMMERSE Dashboard.¹⁷ These include 8 indicators for integration results, covering three of the five dimensions in the dashboard; and 8 indicators for barriers and facilitators, covering four of the six clusters in the dashboard (see Figure 1). We provide here a comparative and intersectional analysis of these indicators based on IMMERSE survey results.¹⁸

Figure 9 Integration results and barriers and facilitators with its dimensions

¹⁷ The Dashboard contains a total of 30 indicators that measure children’s integration results and barriers and facilitators of integration. While 14 of these indicators are extracted from secondary sources and different types of data, the remaining 16 indicators required new data collection with children and schools.

¹⁸ D3.6 provides a full picture of all 30 indicators.

(* Note: the dimensions shown in grey do not contain data from IMMERSE survey results, and thus are not discussed in this report, as they only contain indicators based on secondary sources

Table 2 below summarizes the indicators included in this report. In the sections below we present the results for each of these indicators with a cross-country comparative perspective. The results presented focus on migrant-background children (which includes migrant children and children from migrant parents) and discuss relevant differences between these and non-migrant children in each country. We also discuss relevant differences by intersecting variables of gender and age.

Table 2. Summary of indicators

DIMENSION	INDICATOR
INTEGRATION RESULTS	
<p>Language and culture dimension. This dimension reflects specific domains of cultural adjustment that are fundamental during integration processes</p>	<p>Children’s perceived competence in host country’s language</p> <p>Children maintaining their cultural identity while adopting key host country cultural values and intercultural competencies</p>
<p>Well-being dimension. This dimension reflects children’s subjective hedonic experience of their own lives and their psychosocial adjustment during integration processes</p>	<p>Children’s happiness</p> <p>Children’s sense of belonging in school</p>
<p>Social connections dimension. This dimension relates to the features of the social networks that children maintain with key figures and institutions.</p>	<p>Interconnectedness with friends and peers (support)</p> <p>Interconnectedness with friends and peers (intercultural bridges)</p> <p>Interconnectedness with teachers (support)</p>

	Interconnectedness with institutions (trust)
BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS	
School organization and teachers cluster. School organization and leadership around intercultural competences and inclusive values, parental involvement, or teachers' attitudes and training	Clear leadership and school identity around intercultural values (against xenophobia, prejudice and stereotypes)
	School promotion of parental involvement in school activities, extra-curricular activities, and parental associations
Mental health services cluster. Availability of counselling and therapeutic services in the school or otherwise.	Counselling services at school
Negative attitudes cluster. Children's subjective perceptions and experiences on negative attitudes or mistreatment towards them.	Experience or perception of negative attitudes
	Experience of harassment/physical violence outside the family (bullying)
Learning support cluster. Availability of support in different learning domains and extra-curricular activities at the school and out-of-school contexts, and children's attendance to these services.	Supplementary community services for learning or language support
	Extra-curricular activities or after-class learning centres available

6.1 INTEGRATION RESULTS

6.1.1 LANGUAGE AND CULTURE DIMENSION

CHILDREN'S PERCEIVED COMPETENCE IN HOST COUNTRY'S LANGUAGE

The indicator measures competence in the main language of their country of residence (as perceived and self-declared by children themselves) by combining children's answers about two specific competences (understanding and speaking the host language).¹⁹

Most migrant background children declare having a high level of language competence in all countries (between over 60-70% in most cases). This is much more frequent in Spain (over 80%), which could be explained by the large presence of Spanish-speaking migrant population. And it is less the case in Greece (below 60%). Belgium (62%) represents a particular case, because, unlike other countries our data covers a bilingual reality and children responded to a more complex frame of reference (including both languages).

Considering only statistically significant differences, the level of language competence most frequently differs per **migrant background**.²⁰ The percentage of high competence is lower in first-generation migrant children as compared to second generation and then native children. These differences are smaller in Spain, where all groups show high level of competence (81, 90 and 94% respectively), and the largest in Greece, with 33-39 percentage points of difference (58, 84 and 90% respectively). Belgium represents a particular case, because, unlike other countries our data covers

¹⁹ This question is adapted based on the age of respondents. For younger children (6-9 y.o.) this is measured by asking whether speaking the host country language is "easy", "okay" or "hard" for them. For older children this is measured by asking whether they can explain themselves in the host country language "always or almost always", "sometimes", or "never or almost never". Children's answers are summed and transformed to a score from 1-low to 3-high. In the case of Belgium, the question included both French and Dutch languages to reflect the bilingual reality of the participating sites.

²⁰ No statistically significant differences found in Ireland and Italy.

a bilingual reality and children responded to a more complex frame of reference (including both languages).

Among migrant background children, there are no statistically significant differences in language competence per **gender** (except in Spain and Greece, but with small differences, with slightly better results for girls). Differences by **age** are statistically significant only in Spain, Greece, and Germany, where we find two opposing patterns: in Spain and Greece, the high level of language competence decreases with age; these differences are small in Spain, but very notable in Greece (from 64% among small children to 39% among late adolescents). In contrast, in Germany the high competence in German notably increases with age (52% of small children, to 63% of early adolescents, and further to 69% among middle adolescents and 78% among late adolescents).

CHILDREN MAINTAINING THEIR CULTURAL IDENTITY WHILE ADOPTING KEY HOST COUNTRY CULTURAL VALUES AND INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCIES

This indicator is only collected for older children, as research shows that collective identity begins to develop in adolescence and keeps evolving beyond youth and adulthood (Berzonsky, 2004). The indicator measures whether children (above 10 years old) feel close to people based on different geographical and cultural categories corresponding to their cultures of origin, host country and intersecting social categories. The indicator measures whether children feel close to *both* their cultures of origin and other groups and categories.²¹

²¹ Children select the groups they feel close to from nine different items, which we then group into the 3 relevant categories: culture of origin (people from the same country as their parents, their same language, or their same religion), host country (“People from your neighbourhood”; “People from the city where you live”; “People from [host country]”), and intersecting social categories (“People of your same age”; “People of your same gender”; “People with your same interests and hobbies”).

A varied picture emerges for this indicator, with three different patterns across the six countries. In the most traditional immigration countries (Germany and Belgium) almost 60% of the migrant-background children have such intercultural ties, and this is followed by a large minority (around 30%) who do not feel close to people from their culture of origin. The inverse pattern is found in Italy and Greece, where only 35% have these intercultural ties, and instead almost half of the migrant-background children do not feel close to people from their culture of origin. Spain and Italy are an intermediate case, where each of these types represents approximately 45%. Remarkably, in all six countries, only around 10% of children report feeling close exclusively to their culture of origin.

Differences by **migrant background** are statistically significant in all countries. In most countries, the percentage of children with intercultural ties is larger for first generation than second generation children, while the latter more frequently do not feel close to their culture of origin. These differences are nonetheless small (under 10 percentage points, except in Ireland with 12 percentage points). Belgium shows the inverse pattern, but the differences are marginal (60% v 57%). Both groups of children present very small percentages (below 15%) of children who feel close only to their cultures of origin, being these only marginal (below 5%) in Belgium and Germany. However, in Greece the percentage of those who feel close only to their cultures of origin is notably larger among first generation (21%) than second generation children (11%).²²

Looking at possible variations by **gender** among migrant background children, we only find statistically significant differences in Germany and Belgium, where migrant background girls declare intercultural ties more often than boys (with differences under 10 percentage points). Children who define their gender "in another way" declare intercultural ties notably less in Belgium (difference of 17 percentage points with girls) and slightly more in Germany (6 percentage points). Regarding at variations by **age**, only two opposite and statistically significant patterns emerge: in Spain the percentage of children of migrant-background with intercultural ties increases by age (with a difference of 17 percentage points from small children to late adolescents), while in Greece it decreases (with a difference of 12 percentage points).

²² In the case of native children, this variable might have slightly different interpretations. Only around a quarter (20-32%) declare feeling close to both their cultures of origin and to other groups of people, and most of them do not declare feeling close to their cultures of origin (with percentages above 65%).

6.1.2 WELL-BEING DIMENSION CHILDREN'S HAPPINESS

This indicator reflects the children's evaluation and of their own life experiences as enjoyable and pleasant (Holder, 2012). Children answer one item indicating the degree of happiness that they experience overall.²³

The immense majority of migrant background children across countries declare feeling happy, with percentages above 75%. Ireland is the country with highest percentage of happy children (88%) while Germany presents the lowest (76%). Still, a remarkable proportion of migrant-background children across countries (12-24%) refer feeling unhappy. Considering only statistically significant differences, just Spain and Italy show variations in levels of happiness by **migrant background**, with similar results for first and second-generation children, who report feeling unhappy more frequently than for natives, although the differences are small (under 10 percentage points).

Statistically significant differences by **gender** emerge in Spain, Ireland, and Italy. In these countries the percentage of boys who feel happy is systematically higher than for girls, although with very small differences (4 percentage points). However, the differences are quite dramatic with children who define their gender in another way, who report feeling unhappy three to six times more often (the largest difference occurs in Ireland). Regarding significant variation by **age**, the percentage of unhappy children notably increases across the board from small children to early, middle, and late adolescence, with differences ranging from 14 percentage points in Greece and Belgium to 21 percentage points in Spain.

²³ This question is adapted based on the age of respondents. Both younger and older children are asked to indicate their degree of happiness in general including four options: "very happy"; "quite happy"; "not very happy"; "not at all happy". For younger children the question includes a cartoon-based scale of response options. Older and younger children's answers are summed and transformed to a score from 1-not at all happy to 4-very happy. For reporting purposes, the score is presented in two dichotomic categories: "Unhappy", which combines the "not at all happy" and "not very happy" categories, and "Happy", which combines the categories "quite happy" and "very happy".

CHILDREN'S SENSE OF BELONGING IN SCHOOL

This indicator reflects how much children feel endorsed by and as a part of their school. This is measured through a scale built with several items in which children must respond how frequently they feel like they belong at school, that they can really be themselves at school and like people at their school care about them.²⁴

Whereas in Spain, Ireland and Greece half or more of the migrant-background children declare a high level of belonging in their schools (50-58%), this percentage notably decreases in Germany, Italy and Belgium (35-43%). Conversely, in the latter countries more children declare a medium level of belonging (over 50%). Overall, only marginal proportions of children (below 10%) report low levels of belonging. Statistically significant differences by **migrant background** emerge only in Spain and Ireland. Both countries show a common pattern: high level of belonging at school diminishes from native children to second-generation, and first-generation migrant children, although the differences are small (9 percentage points in each).

We only observe statistically significant differences among migrant background children by **gender** in Spain and Italy. We find a pattern of small differences between boys and girls, in which migrant

²⁴ This question is adapted based on the age of respondents. For younger children this is measured by asking how often four different statements occur to them ("I feel like I belong at my school"; "I can really be myself at school"; "I feel like other children at my school care about me"; "I feel like other teachers at my school care about me") in a scale from "almost never", to "sometimes", and "almost always". The younger children's questionnaire includes cartoon-based response options with each statement. For older this is measured by asking how often three different statements occur to them ("I feel like I belong at my school"; "I can really be myself at school"; "I feel like people at my school care about me") in a scale from "almost never", to "sometimes", and "almost always". Children's responses are summed and transformed to a score from 1-low to 3-high.

boys present higher levels of belonging more often than girls (under 10 percentage points), and notable differences compared with children who define their gender in another way (ranging from 12 to 29 percentage points). Variations by **age**, statistically significant in all countries but Germany and Belgium, follow a common pattern: the high level of belonging at school notably diminishes as migrant-background children grow (from percentages of around 70% of small children to 30-50% in middle and late adolescents).

6.1.3 SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS DIMENSION

INTERCONNECTEDNESS WITH FRIENDS AND PEERS (SUPPORT):

This indicator measures the quality of relationships between the children and their friends and peers in terms of social support. This is calculated through a scale built with several items in which children must respond how frequently they feel that their friends help them, they can talk with their friends about their feelings, and that their friends would stand up for them when needed.²⁵

Over half of the migrant-background children surveyed declare high levels of support from friends and peers in all countries except Italy (41% vs 52-61%). Overall, only marginal proportions of children (below 10%) report low levels of support from friends and peers in all six countries. Considering only statistically significant differences by **migrant background**, the high level of support from friends diminishes from native children to second-generation, and to first-generation

²⁵ This question is adapted based on the age of respondents. For both younger and older children this is measured by asking how often three different statements occur to them (“My friends really try to help me”; “I can talk with my friends about what makes me happy and sad”; “My friends stand up for me if someone mistreats me”) to which they must respond in a scale from “Never or almost never”, to “Sometimes”, and “Always or almost always”. The younger children’s questionnaire includes cartoon-based response options with each statement. Children’s responses are summed and combined into a score from 1-low to 3-high.

migrant children in Spain, Ireland, Italy and Greece. These are notable differences ranging from 19 to 7 percentage points. A different pattern emerges in Germany, where second-generation migrant children present the largest percentage of children reporting high levels of support from friends and peers (68%), which diminishes in non-migrants (58%) followed closely by first-generation migrant children (55%).

Looking at possible variations by **gender** among migrant background children, we observe statistically significant differences in Spain, Ireland, Greece, and Germany. In all countries girls more often declare high levels of support from friends and peers than boys (differences range from 6 to 14 percentage points). The most remarkable differences are found for children defining their gender “in another way”, who are much more less likely to declare high levels of support from friends and peers (between 15 and 27 percentage points relative to girls). The exception to this is Germany, where these children register the highest percentage with high levels of support, above girls (4 percentage points). Regarding variations by **age**, we only find statistically significant differences in Spain and Greece. The percentage of migrant children with a high level of support from friends and peers notably diminishes as they grow: from 65% in small children to just above 50% in middle and late adolescents.

INTERCONNECTEDNESS WITH FRIENDS AND PEERS (BRIDGES)

This indicator is only collected for older children, as research shows children develop representations of social categories (Rhodes & Baron, 2019). This indicator measures the diversity of children’s friends and peer groups, by asking children (above 10 years) old how many of their friends are born in a different country or from a different culture.²⁶

²⁶ Older children are presented with two items (“How many of your friends were born in a different country than you?” and “How many of your friends are from a different culture (beliefs, customs, traditions, ways of eating, etc.) than you?”) with five response options (“All of them”; “Most of them”; “A few”; “None”; “I don’t have any friends”). Older children’s responses are combined in a scale from 0-No to 2-Many, in which the category “Many” includes all “All of them” or “Most of them” responses to the two questions, the category “A few” includes all “a few” responses in the two questions, and the category “No” includes all “None” or “I don’t have any friends” responses to the two questions.

Two different patterns emerge across countries: in the more recent immigration countries (Spain, Ireland, Greece and Italy) less than half of the migrant-background children (40-49%) declare having many friends born in a different country or from a different culture. While in traditional immigration countries (Germany and Belgium) this percentage increases to 59-60%. And conversely, the inverse patterns are registered for children with only a few of these friends. Across all countries, only a marginal proportion of children (under 10%) declare not having any friends born in a different country or from a different culture (with only Greece reaching 11%).

Considering only statistically significant differences by **migrant background**, in all countries the percentage of children with many friends born in a different country or from a different culture considerably increases among migrant-background children relative to native children (differences range between 14-32 in percentage points), and from second-generation to first-generation migrant children (differences in percentage points go from 10-18).

We only observe statistically significant differences by **gender** among migrant background children in Spain and Germany, but with opposite patterns. In Spain, children who define their gender in another way have the most of these friends, followed by girls and boys, although the differences are small (below 10 percentage points). In Germany, the opposite relationship holds, and children who define their gender in another way are notably less likely than girls and boys to have many friends born in a different country or from a different culture than girls (33% v 58-63% respectively). Regarding variations by **age**, we only observe statistically significant differences among migrant background children in Belgium and Greece. The two countries present opposite patterns: while in Belgium the percentage of children with many friends born in a different country or from a different culture increases with age (from 41% of small children to 51% of early adolescence and 66-65% of middle and late adolescents), in Greece it slightly diminishes (from 42-44% of small children to early adolescence and 36% of middle and late adolescents).

INTERCONNECTEDNESS WITH TEACHERS (SUPPORT)

This indicator measures the quality of relationships between the children and their teachers in terms of social support. This is calculated through a scale built with several items in which children must respond how frequently they feel that their teachers help them, they can talk with them about their feelings, and that they would stand up for them when needed.²⁷

While in Spain, Ireland and Greece approximately 60% of the migrant-background children declare high levels of support from teachers, this percentage decreases to roughly half of the sample in Italy, Belgium and Germany (47-51%). And the inverse pattern is repeated for children declaring medium levels of support. Across countries, only marginal proportions of children (below 10%) report low levels of support from teachers. Only the results in Belgium and Greece yielded statistically significant differences by **migrant background**. First-generation migrant children declare the highest support from teachers in these countries, followed by non-migrant children, and then second-generation migrant children. These differences are small (under 10 percentage points) except in Belgium (with 14 percentage points between first-generation and second-generation children).

Looking at possible variations by **gender** among migrant background children, we observe statistically significant differences only in Spain, showing that girls declare more often a high level of support from teachers than boys (5 percentage points), and that children who define their gender (14 percentage points compared with the girls). Regarding variations by **age**, statistically significant

²⁷ This question is adapted based on the age of respondents. For both younger and older children this is measured by asking how often three different statements occur to them (“My teachers really try to help me”; “Most of my teachers really listen to what I have to say”; “My teachers stand up for me if someone mistreats me”) to which they must respond in a scale from “Never or almost never”, to “Sometimes”, and “Always or almost always”. The younger children’s questionnaire includes cartoon-based response options with each statement. Children’s responses are summed and combined into a score from 1-low to 3-high.

differences appeared in all countries but Belgium. The percentage of children declaring a high level of support from teachers notably diminishes as they grow: from percentages of high support above 70-80% in small children (except in Germany with 64%), to above 30-50% in middle and late adolescents. The differences between age stages range between 28-35 percentage points, with the exception of Germany, where the difference is reduced to 18 percentage points.

INTERCONNECTEDNESS WITH INSTITUTIONS (TRUST)

This indicator measures children’s trust towards three institutions essential in the lives of children: education (teachers and schools), healthcare (doctors and hospitals) and law and order systems (police, judges, courts, etc.). This indicator was adapted with more simple answer options for younger children. ²⁸

Trust in teachers and schools

Most migrant-background children trust teachers and schools. However, there seem to be two groups of countries with notable differences in their levels of trust in schools: Germany and Belgium have lower levels (around 55%) than Spain, Ireland, and Greece (around 72%). The levels of distrust are also particularly high (close to 20%) in the first group. Considering only statistically significant differences, the levels of trust in teachers and schools significantly differ per **migrant background** in Germany, Greece and Belgium. First-generation migrant children always show the highest levels of trust in schools and teachers, followed by children without a migrant background

²⁸ Older children responded how much they trust these three institutions (a. teachers and schools; b. doctors and hospitals; and 3. Police and the justice system) in a scale from 0 to 10, while younger children were asked about their trust in the same three systems with the answer options ‘yes’ or ‘no’, as the scale proved too abstract for this age group during questionnaire testing. The levels of the scale were divided into the following categories: No trust at all (value 0), Distrust (values from 1-4), Neutral (value 5), Trust (6-9) and Complete trust (value 10).

(this difference ranges between 2-16 percentage points across countries) and second-generation migrant children (difference range of 0-13 percentage points).

We find statistically significant differences per **gender** in all countries except Belgium. Migrant-background boys trust teachers slightly more than girls (with a small difference range of 4-8 percentage points). These differences notably increase for children who define their gender “in another way” (difference range of 12-24 percentage points). In Greece and Ireland these differences are dramatic, ranging from 35-58 percentage points.

We find statistically significant differences per **age** in all countries, where the shared pattern is that the levels of trust considerably diminish from small migrant-background children to early adolescents (with a difference range of 16-45 points). The levels of trust keep diminishing and the differences between age groups become smaller as children grow. In Greece however, the level of trust of late adolescents notably increases when compared to middle adolescents in 18 percentage points, which shifts from the trend shared by the other countries.

Trust in doctors and hospitals

The immense majority of migrant-background children trust doctors and hospitals in all six countries, ranging between 69 and 81%. In fact, the health system is the most trusted among the migrant-background children across all countries. Spain and Ireland hold the highest level, while Germany and Belgium hold the lowest, still representing over two-thirds of all migrant-background children in those countries. Differences in the levels of trust in doctors and hospitals per **migrant background** are statistically significant in all countries but Belgium. A consistent pattern is found: trust in doctors diminishes from natives to second-generation migrants (differences under 5 percentage points) and to first-generation migrants (differences ranging between 5 and 11 percentage points relative to non-migrants). The largest difference is found in Spain and Ireland.

We also find statistically significant differences per **gender** (except in Italy and Belgium). Migrant-background boys trust doctors and hospitals more than girls (with a difference range of 1-13 percentage points). And the levels of trust dramatically decrease in migrant-background children who define their gender “in another way” (with a difference range of 30-53 percentage points), except in Spain, where the difference is small. We find statistically significant differences per **age** in all countries except in Belgium. The shared pattern is that the levels of trust among migrant-background children notably diminish from small children to early adolescents (with a difference range of 13-27 points, except for Ireland where this difference is only of 4 percentage points). Overall, the levels of trust on doctors keep diminishing (although the differences between age groups become smaller) as children grow. In Greece however, the level of trust of late adolescents notably increases in 14 percentage points when compared to middle adolescents, which shifts from the trend shared by the other countries.

Trust in police and the justice system

Most migrant-background children trust the police and justice system with figures hovering around 60-70% in all countries. Still, the justice system is the least trusted (behind schools and doctors) among the migrant-background children across all countries. Ireland holds the highest percentage of migrant-background children trusting police and the justice system (70%), while Germany and Belgium hold the lowest percentage (55%), still representing over half of all migrant-background children in those countries. Considering only statistically significant differences, differences by **migrant-background** emerge in Spain, Germany and Greece, and they follow very different patterns. Spain and Greece show opposite patterns: while the levels of trust diminish by migrant background in Spain (first-generation children trust the least the police, and native children the most), the trend in Greece is the opposite (native children trust the least the police, and first generation the most). These differences are nonetheless small (3-7 percentage points). In Germany, the levels of trust in

the police are identical for natives and first-generation migrant children, but they notably diminish for second-generation migrant children (with a difference of 16 percentage points).

We find statistically significant differences per **gender** only in all Spain and Italy, and with opposite patterns: the levels of trust among migrant-background children are higher for girls in Spain and for boys in Italy, although these differences are very small (3-5 percentage points). In both cases, the levels of trust notably decrease in among those who describe their gender “in another way”, (with a difference range of 19-24 percentage points). We find statistically significant differences per **age** in all countries, where levels of trust among migrant-background children notably (and in some cases quite dramatically) diminish from small to early adolescents (with a difference range of 13-40 points). Overall, the levels of trust keep diminishing and the differences between age groups become smaller as children grow. In Greece however, the level of trust notably rises from middle to late adolescence (with a difference of 22 percentage points), departing from the trend shared by the other countries, where this difference is small or very small (with a difference range of 0-10 percentage points).

6.2 BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS

6.2.1 SCHOOL ORGANISATION AND TEACHERS CLUSTER

CLEAR LEADERSHIP AND SCHOOL IDENTITY AROUND INTERCULTURAL VALUES (AGAINST XENOPHOBIA, PREJUDICE AND STEREOTYPES)

This variable measures the importance of intercultural values for schools (according to schools' principals and according to teachers).²⁹ The data below presents answers for each school, both from principals (one per school), and from teachers (several per school).³⁰

Note: the sample size for directors in Germany and Belgium is extremely small (n=8 and 11 respectively), so the results from these countries are purely descriptive of these few schools and not indicative of the wider context in these countries, and for that reason are shown in cursive font and cannot be considered as reliable.

²⁹ For both, principals and teachers, this is measured by asking about the importance of the following aspects for their school: educational excellence and/or student's results, educational innovation, intercultural values (e.g. appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness and tolerance) and other types of ethical values (e.g. religious, civic). In the case of teachers, this is referred to how schools are presented to parents who approach the school for the first time. The response options for each item are: “not very important”, “somewhat important”, “very important”, and “this is one of our insignias”. The teachers' scores in each school are averaged and presented per school.

³⁰ The teachers' scores in each school are averaged and grouped per school.

Intercultural values as part of syllabus (by principals)

Intercultural values as part of lessons (by teachers)

Most school **principals** declare that intercultural values (e.g., appreciation of diversity, cultural awareness, openness, and tolerance) are one of the insignias of their schools in all countries. This percentage is sensibly lower *in Belgium and Greece* (45-49%) than in the other countries, and Spain registers a particularly high percentage (86%). However, **teachers** in each site were asked the same question, and these results were very different from the principal's answers across all IMMERSE countries. In all countries, less than half of the schools have intercultural values as one of the insignias according to their teachers. This percentage is sensibly lower in Italy (29%) and it is the highest in *Belgium, Germany and Spain* (50%, 48%, 49%). Still, according to teachers in Italy, intercultural values are very important for 70% of their schools.

SCHOOL PROMOTION OF PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL ACTIVITIES, EXTRA-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES AND PARENTAL ASSOCIATIONS

This variable measures the proportion of schools that, according to their principals, offer a variety of channels for parental involvement (up to four).³¹ Additionally, principals also informed on how many of these channels are adapted to migrant parent’s needs (e.g., language, culture, etc.).

Note: the sample size of schools with directors’ responses in Germany and Belgium are extremely small (n=7 and 8 respectively), so the results from these countries are purely descriptive of these few schools and not indicative of the wider context in these countries, and for that reason will be shown in cursive font.

Number of channels for parental involvement in school life

Number of channels adapted to parents

³¹ Principals were presented with four different types of activities and responded whether they were offered to the parents or not: information on child’s progress; requests and ideas to help students at home with homework; requests to volunteer and participate in school-related activities; and channels to participate in decision-making.

The majority of schools, according to their principals, provide all four **channels for parental involvement** in all six countries. However, there are significant variations in this percentage: while most countries hover around 70%, in Ireland, 90% of schools provide all four considered channels (and all remaining schools provide three), which is outstanding among all six countries. *In contrast the percentage decreases to 63% in Belgium.* In contrast, when considering how many **channels are adapted for parents' needs** (e.g., language, culture, etc.), the main pattern across IMMERSE countries is that the majority of schools do not offer any of these channels adapted for parents' needs (50-65%), with the exceptions of *Germany (14%) and Italy (44%). However, in Germany, the immense majority of the sampled schools (86%) have adapted at least 1-2 channels for parents' needs, which is well above the average.*

INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE AS PART OF SYLLABUS OR/AND TRANSVERSALLY

This indicator looks into teachers' and principals' perceptions about the integration of intercultural competence in the school (as part of the syllabus or transversally). Both principals and teachers were presented with five topics. Principals were asked whether the school curriculum included a series of topics related to intercultural competence (up to 5), and teachers were asked if they included opportunities to promote these in their lessons.³² The data below presents answers for each school, both from principals (one per school), and from teachers (several per school).³³

Note: the sample size of schools with directors' responses in Germany and Belgium are extremely small (n=7 and 8 respectively), so the results from these countries are purely descriptive of these few schools and not indicative of the wider context in these countries, and for that reason will be shown in cursive font.

Intercultural competence as part of syllabus (by principals)

³² Principals and teachers were presented with four different topics and responded whether each of these were included in the school curriculum: communicating with people from different cultures or countries; knowledge of different cultures; knowledge of different religions; respect for cultural diversity; and recognizing cultural prejudice and stereotypes.

³³ The teachers' scores in each school are averaged and grouped per school.

Intercultural competence as part of lessons (by teachers)

Most school **principals** declare that their school's syllabus includes all 5 topics on intercultural values in all countries *except in Germany, where a similar majority declare including only 4*. In most country this percentage hovers around 70%. However, it is sensibly lower Greece (60%) and it is higher in Italy and Belgium (81%, 88%). However, the results for the inclusion of these topics in the schools' classes, according to their **teachers**, are slightly different, with variations across countries. Only in Italy still a large majority (76%) declare including all five topics in their lessons (and all remaining teachers declare they include four). In most other countries the percentage is reduced to 50-59%, although a large percentage also includes four (25%-31%). Finally, in Spain and Italy the percentage that includes all five topics decreases to 32-33% (although roughly the remaining part of their samples includes four).

6.2.2 MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES CLUSTER
 COUNSELLING SERVICES AT SCHOOL

This indicator measures the available resources concerning counselling services at school. We divide schools into three categories: those with no personnel dedicated to psycho-social support

available, those with some part-time psycho-social support, and those with some full-time psycho-social support.³⁴

Note: the sample size of schools with directors' responses in Germany and Belgium are extremely small (n=8 and 9 respectively), so the results from these countries are purely descriptive of these few schools and not indicative of the wider context in these countries, and for that reason will be shown in cursive font.

According to their principals, the average pattern across IMMERSE countries is that around half of schools do not have any staff to offer **psycho-social support or personal counselling** to students. Greece stands out with only 33% of schools declaring this absence: in turn, 77% of their school principals indicate that they have full-time or part-time psycho-social or counselling staff. Ireland stands at the other extreme, where only 35% of schools have any staff to offer this kind of support.

6.2.3 NEGATIVE ATTITUDES

EXPERIENCE OR PERCEPTION OF NEGATIVE ATTITUDES

This indicator explores children's perceptions of their treatment by others. In particular, children were asked if they avoided certain places for fear of being mistreated.³⁵ This question was only asked to older children.

³⁴ This indicator was measured using two different questions posed to principals regarding the number of staff the school had for psycho-social support/personal counselling and for academic counselling/guidance, in full-time and part-time positions. The results indicate the share of schools with some staff dedicated to psycho-social support or personal counselling.

³⁵ Children were asked if they avoid certain places for fear of being treated badly. The answer options included; 1) yes; 2) sometimes, and 3) no. The indicator is calculated adding up the first and second answer options into a single category that gathers all avoidances of situations for fear of being treated badly.

A large minority of the migrant-background children in all countries avoid places for fear of being treated badly. This percentage ranges between 42-48%, except in the case of Spain, where the percentage diminishes to 33%, which is still a sizeable proportion. Statistically significant differences by **migrant background** emerge in Greece, Italy and Spain. In all three countries, the avoidance of places for fear of being treated badly increases by migrant background. However, the differences between first-, second-generation migrant background and native children are very small (from 0 to 5 percentage points). In Germany we find an unusual pattern, where second-generation migrant children avoid places notably less often than other children, with a difference of 15 percentage points.

We find statistically significant differences per **gender** in Ireland, Italy and Spain. All three follow the same pattern, where migrant-background girls avoid places for fear to a larger extent than boys, although this difference is small (with a difference range from 3-10 percentage points); and children who define their gender “in another way” avoid places more frequently, notably in Spain and Italy (with a difference range of 15-23 percentage points) and less so in Ireland (4 percentage points). We find statistically significant differences per **age** in Germany and Spain only, where the shared pattern is that the avoidance of places diminishes with age, although the differences are very small (with a difference range of 0-8 percentage points).

EXPERIENCE OF HARASSMENT/PHYSICAL VIOLENCE OUTSIDE THE FAMILY

This indicator explores experiences of bullying.³⁶ It is important to note that the question on whether they have experienced bullying was presented to children without a pre-definition of this term, and that the data below brings together all positive answers, considering those who declared having experienced this a few times and many times. We thus expect the indicator to reflect children’s perceived sense of mistreatment by peers, even if it might not match the strictest definitions of bullying.

A large minority of the migrant-background children declare having been bullied at some point, representing a pattern that ranges between 33% (Spain and Greece) and 47% (Ireland). Statistically significant differences per **migrant background** emerge only in Belgium, Germany and Spain, where we find two opposing patterns. On the one hand, in Belgium and Germany experiences of bullying are less common among migrant-background children: these experiences slightly decrease from native children to second-generation children (around 5 percentage points) and further to first-generation children, who are the least likely to declare having experienced bullying (with a remarkable 18 percentage points difference in the case of Belgium). The situation is inverted in Spain, where experiences of bullying are more common among migrant-background children relative to native children (7-8 percentage points respectively).

We find statistically significant differences per **gender** in bullying in all countries. They follow the same pattern, where migrant-background girls have been bullied more than boys, although this difference is small (with a difference range of 4-10 percentage points). Children who define their gender “in another way” are the group that claims they have been bullied the most, and the

³⁶ The question asked to both younger and older children is “Have you been bullied in [host country] by your schoolmates at school, or peers outside of school or online?”, and the answer options were divided into three levels: 1) no, never; 2) a few times; 3) many times. The indicator is calculated adding up the second and third answer options into a single category that gathers all experiences of bullying, whether “many times” or “a few times”.

differences with girls range from very small (in Italy) to dramatically large (in Germany), with a difference in percentage points ranging from 5 to 33. Exceptionally, this group in Belgium reports lower levels of bullying than girls, although the difference is marginal. We find statistically significant differences per **age** in Italy, Belgium, Ireland and, where the shared pattern is that the experience of bullying diminishes with age. These differences range from 1-22 percentage points. The differences between small children and early adolescents in Belgium is notable, with a difference of 26 percentage points.

6.2.4 LEARNING SUPPORT CLUSTER

SUPPLEMENTARY COMMUNITY SERVICES FOR LEARNING OR LANGUAGE SUPPORT

This indicator measures if children participate in after-school learning or language support in their schools and outside of schools.³⁷

In most countries, around half of migrant-background children declare attending language or learning support either at school or in the neighbourhood, with a range between 45-54%. In Ireland however, this percentage is notably lower (31%), and in Greece it is notably higher (68%). Considering only statistically significant differences, attendance to after-school learning or language support significantly differs per **migrant background** in all countries. The level of attendance increases per migrant-background in all countries, although differences are very small (ranging from 0-8 percentage points) from natives to second-generation children (except for Italy,

³⁷ Older children were asked in-school and outside-of-school versions of the question, "Other than Covid-related closures and restrictions, are there services available that provide learning support for students (to help them with homework, language learning, etc.)?". They could answer: "Yes, and I do use them", "Yes, but I do not use them", "No, there is nothing I can afford/access", "No, there are no such services", or "I don't know". The younger children were asked simplified versions of these questions and could answer with "yes" or "no". The indicator is calculated considering whether they use these services or not.

where it is notable, with a 15%) and small to notable from second- to first-generation migrant children (ranging from 2 to 19 percentage points).

We find no statistically significant differences per **gender** except in Belgium and Italy, and in these cases the differences are not large, with migrant background boys attending these services more often than girls (around 6-10 percentage points difference). While migrant-background children who describe their gender in another way in Belgium attend these services slightly more often than girls, in Italy they do it notably less often (with a difference of 20 percentage points). We find statistically significant differences per **age** in all countries except for Belgium, where the shared pattern is that the attendance to after-school language and learning support diminishes with age and it slightly increases again in late adolescence (with a difference range of 2-5 percentage points). Ireland is an exception to this pattern, since attendance notably increases from small children to early adolescents (with a 20-percentage point difference).

EXTRA-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES OR AFTER-CLASS LEARNING CENTRES AVAILABLE

This indicator measures if children participate in after-school extra-curricular activities (such as sport, music, art, etc.) in their schools and outside of schools.³⁸

A majority of migrant background children in all countries declare attending extra-curricular activities or after-school learning either at school or in the neighbourhood, with a range between 59% (Belgium, Italy, Spain) and 70% (Ireland). Considering only statistically significant differences,

³⁸ Older children were asked in-school and outside-of-school versions of the question, “Other than during Covid-related school closures and restrictions, does your school have after-school activities (such as sports, arts, music, etc.)?”. They could answer: “Yes, and I do use them”, “Yes, but I do not use them”, “No, there is nothing I can afford/access”, “No, there are no such services”, or “I don’t know”. The younger children were asked simplified versions of these questions and could answer with “yes” or “no”. The indicator is calculated considering whether they use these services or not.

we find no differences per **migrant background** in the attendance to extra-curricular or after-school learning activities except for Spain, where this attendance diminishes per migrant-background, although the differences are not very large (from 68% of native children, to 60-59% of second and first-generation migrant children).

We find statistically significant differences per **gender** in Belgium, Italy, Greece and Spain. In all four countries, the level of attendance to these extra-curricular activities among migrant-background children diminishes from boys to girls, with small to notable differences (ranging from 9-19 percentage points). While these levels keep decreasing in Belgium and Spain for children who describe their gender in another way, the opposite pattern is found in Italy and Greece, with notable differences in both patterns ranging from 7 to 21 percentage points. We find statistically significant differences per **age** in all countries, where the shared pattern is that the attendance to extra-curricular activities of migrant-background children diminishes with age. These differences range from very small to very notable (from 3-23 percentage points). It is interesting to point out that in the case of Greece and Belgium the attendance increases again in late adolescence, although the differences are small (5-7 percentage points)

7 Conclusion

a. Reflections on methodological issues

The IMMERSE quantitative data collection has achieved a unique large-scale cross-country dataset on migrant and refugee children in Europe. The database that IMMERSE has produced is a rich and extremely valuable source of information on the lives of over 24,000 children, almost 60% of whom are from a refugee or migrant background. This constitutes the largest survey implemented in Europe targeting migrant-background children and including children since age 7. The database will be open to researchers, policy-makers and the wider public, and will allow making specific and in-depth analyses on a broad number of issues relevant for these children's integration and for designing relevant policies.

The foundations of this data collection are rooted in the IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators and the co-creation process through which the dashboard was developed. The dimensions, clusters and set of indicators defined in the dashboard, and the normative framework under which it was developed (namely, the highest European and international standards pursuing equality and

children's rights), have facilitated a high degree of harmonisation in terms of the main contents and the target population to be considered. As noted in Section 4, the design of the questionnaires particularly benefitted from the co-creation process leading to the development of the Dashboard of indicators, and it was adjusted to reflect and respond to the heterogeneity of refugee and migrant children's profiles (by origin, by developmental stage) in Europe.

Even more challenging was the implementation of a common sampling framework. As noted in Section 5, the outbreak of COVID-19 and the Ukrainian crisis, and differences in educational and reception systems, regional bureaucratic procedures, regional responses to Covid-19, and several other factors affected the harmonisation of sampling and fieldwork. To accomplish the data collection and reach targets, the IMMERSE partners had to be flexible and creative in their approach to recruitment and accommodation of site requests and conditions of participation. While this resulted in a lower degree of harmonisation across sampling and fieldwork than was originally envisioned.

Large-scale and cross-country studies can provide an important evidence-based contribution to policy-making and to our understanding of the lived-experiences of migrant children and other vulnerable populations (Conference of European Statisticians Task Force, 2022). However, this type of research also presents methodological challenges that require exploration, because they can affect children's inclusion. These challenges included: significant data gaps around education systems and student populations within countries and at European level (UNESCO, 2017); differing national interpretations and implementation of GDPR legislation (Milkaite & Lievens, 2019); differing policies and practices on consent for children's participation in research; and differing practices regarding gatekeeping for children's participation in research, in schools and other environments.

Each of these issues represents not only challenges to the methodological integrity of cross-national research in Europe, but also potential barriers to children's participation in research, particularly children from vulnerable populations. These are questions pertinent to inclusion, as well as methodology. As the importance of pan-European research in education continues to grow, it is critical that conversations around methodology and children's participation take place at a European level. Minimum standards of available data and an agreed European consensus on consent for child participation in research would support data harmonization processes for large-scale cross-national research projects in Europe (UNESCO, 2017) and support children's right to participation in research that will affect their lives (Lundy & McEvoy, 2012).

b. Conclusions on quantitative survey findings

The quantitative findings from IMMERSE present a complex picture of integration for children with migrant backgrounds in education settings in Europe with many different factors impacting their sense of belonging and socio-educational integration in schools.

Integration Results

Language and culture. The majority of migrant children indicate that they have high levels of **competence in the main language** of their country of residence, which is important to support their social and academic engagement. However, the percentage of high competence is lower in first-generation migrant children (Spain, Germany, Belgium and Greece). Proficiency in the language of the host/receiving country has been found to play a key role in the migrant-native achievement gap across a number of studies (Turney & Kao, 2009; Kristen et al., 2011). Consequently, providing language support is imperative to assist first-generation migrant children in acquiring the host language, thereby facilitating their integration into the host society.

The findings regarding how children maintain their **cultural identity** while adapting to the cultural values of their host country, as well as their development of intercultural competencies, present a multifaceted scenario that is influenced by the unique migration histories of different nations and by migration status. Contrasting first- and second- generation children, the former are more likely to report a strong sense of connection to both their cultures of origin and to other social groups than second-generation children, while the latter have a higher tendency to not feel close to their culture of origin. Very small proportions of migrant-background children feel exclusively close to their culture of origin. In countries with a more established tradition of immigration, Germany and Belgium, the majority of migrant-background children report intercultural ties, while in more recent waves of immigration, such as Spain, Ireland, Greece, and Italy, this percentage diminishes in favour of those who do not feel close to their culture of origin. Overall, there is a significant minority of migrant children who do not feel close to people from their culture of origin and this is important to note as connections to host country and country of origin are important for positive educational (Timm, 2016) and psycho-social outcomes (Berry et al., 2006).

Well-being: In general, migrant children self-reported high levels of **happiness**, with slight variations observed in Spain and Italy, where migrant children reported slightly lower levels of happiness compared to non-migrant children. Age and gender also play a role in happiness levels, with

reported happiness decreasing as children grow older and migrant boys expressing higher levels of happiness than migrant girls. While the overall findings regarding happiness are positive for migrant children, there is a slightly contrasting picture when it comes to their **sense of 'belonging at school'**, where there is larger variation across countries, and which is also influenced by their migrant background. While migrant-background children generally report a strong sense of belonging, statistically significant differences exist in Spain and Ireland. Furthermore, the intersection of gender, age, and migration status is a significant factor affecting feelings of belonging, with migrant boys slightly more likely to report a higher sense of belonging than girls, and a decline in this sense of belonging as children age. These intersections underscore the importance of considering age and gender when providing support for the socio-educational integration of migrant children as the need for belonging and social acceptance is fundamental, especially for adolescent well-being (Raabe, 2019).

Social Connections: The dimension of social connectedness pertains to the nature of children's social networks involving significant individuals and institutions. The extent to which migrant children perceive a sense of belonging in school intersects with their interactions with staff, fellow students, and the overall school environment, as highlighted in studies by Correa-Velez, Gifford, and Barnett (2010) and Hart (2009). Conducting direct research on social connectedness with children is imperative for gaining insights into the experiences of migrant children. Concerning **peer support** and connectedness, more than half of the surveyed children with migrant backgrounds express high levels of support from their friends and peers. However, in Italy, children report lower rates of high support compared to other countries. Differences emerge in the data when considering first- and second-generation migrant children, with age and gender emerging as influential factors in how children perceive support from their friends and peers. A noteworthy finding from the survey is that in all countries, the percentage of children with many **friends born in different countries or from different cultures** significantly increases among those with migrant backgrounds, while native children tend to have fewer such connections. Migrant participants report having more friends from diverse cultures and countries of origin, raising important questions about policies supporting two-way integration and how to encourage diversity in children's relationships and fostering social bridges for migrant and non-migrant children.

In relation to **interconnectedness with teachers**, the majority of migrant children reported high levels of support from their teachers, with children from Italy reporting the lowest levels of support.

Overall, a very small proportion of migrant children report low levels of support from their teachers which is positive. Similar to other findings there are some differences in perceived support from teachers related to gender, age and first- and second-generation migrant background. Overall, the results on **institutional trust** demonstrate high levels of trust in societal institutions for children with migrant backgrounds, with healthcare institutions being the most trusted institution. These findings are promising because mistrust of authorities and governmental systems, such as hospitals, among migrant children and their families can hinder access to integration-supporting services (Heidi et al., 2011). Interestingly, first-generation migrant background children in a number of countries had higher levels of trust in teachers and schools than their peers, indicating the important role that schools play in integration processes for migrant children. Moreover, there are variations in trust levels in teachers and schools across different countries, prompting important questions about how to bolster such trust at the national level. The police and justice system were the least trusted institutions among migrant children, with varying results at the country level, including differences in trust levels between first- and second-generation migrants. Gender and age also exerted an influence on the levels of institutional trust reported by the study participants across all areas.

Barriers and facilitators of integration

School organisation and teachers: There is a notably high level of support among school principals and directors for **promoting intercultural values** in their educational settings, which is a positive finding, albeit with some variations at the country level. However, a significant finding across all participating countries is that teachers were less likely to view intercultural values as one of the most prominent values of their school compared to the principals and directors. Similarly, teachers reported lower levels of **intercultural competence being incorporated into their lessons** compared to the views expressed by principals about the syllabus. This discrepancy suggests a disconnect between the views of principals and teachers regarding the significance of intercultural values and competencies, potentially highlighting deficiencies in leadership concerning intercultural values within schools and challenges in implementation. This points to a potential need for increased support in initial teacher education and Continuous Professional Development, aimed at equipping teachers with the essential skills and knowledge required to effectively implement intercultural values in the curriculum, as suggested by Eurydice in 2019.

The results related to **parental involvement** indicate that the majority of the schools offer a high number of channels or ways for parents to become involved in their children's school. However, there is a discernible trend of limited adaptation of these channels to cater to the specific needs of migrant parents, including considerations for language and cultural aspects. Enhancing outcomes for migrant children can be achieved by fostering the integration of parents within the school community, as emphasized by Crul and Schneider (2010). The survey results suggest a potential requirement to bolster support for the intercultural adaptation of parental involvement channels, which may include the provision of translation support and other forms of assistance.

Mental health services. Access to **counselling** is an important indicator of mental health support for migrant children and the results indicate that there are low levels of availability of counselling and therapeutic services in the school. On average, across the IMMERSE countries, approximately half of the schools lack staff members who can provide psycho-social support or personal counselling to students, although there are some variations at the country level.

Negative Attitudes: Regarding **children's subjective perceptions and experiences of mistreatment** by others, a large minority of migrant-background children express fear of being treated poorly, leading them to avoid certain places. There are variations in this fear across countries. Related to this, a notable minority of migrant-background children report having been bullied at some point in their lives. Spain and Greece have the lowest percentages of **bullying** experienced, while Ireland registers the highest percentage. Being subjected to bullying has been associated with reduced happiness for migrant background children, as highlighted by Correa-Velez et al. (2010). These experiences of peer bullying are intertwined with broader attitudes towards migrants in destination countries.

Learning Supports: In all IMMERSE countries, migrant children had higher attendance rates at **after-school learning or language support programs** compared to their non-migrant peers. Age plays a significant role in determining participation in these support services, with older children in all countries, except Ireland, being less likely to engage with them. Both formal (e.g., learning support) and informal (e.g., extracurricular) support systems generally yield positive effects on students' academic and social development (Fertig in 2012) and it is positive that migrant children are engaging with these supports. The importance of learning supports was especially evident during the Covid-19 pandemic when the closure of schools and distance learning encouraged the reproduction of social inequalities between migrant and non-migrant learners (Gornik et al., 2020).

A large majority of all migrant background children reported attending **extra-curricular activities** either at school or in the neighbourhood. Importantly, there was no significant difference in participation between children from migrant and non-migrant backgrounds. Participating in extra-curricular activity was viewed as a means of creating social connections to peers and to the wider community for migrant youth (Jiang & Peguero, 2017) and it is positive to see these levels of engagement in such activities by migrant children in the study. Gender and age were influencing factors in children's participation in these activities.

In sum, these findings reveal a complex and multifaceted landscape of socio-educational integration for children with migrant backgrounds in European education settings. While there are positive trends, such as high levels of happiness and participation in support programs, there are also challenges, including language disparities, varying levels of belonging, and experiences of mistreatment. Recognizing the influence of age, gender, and migration status is essential for effective support and the successful socio-educational integration of migrant children. Addressing these complexities will contribute to more inclusive and equitable educational environments for all children.

8 References

AIDA/ECRE (2023) Access to Education: Belgium. Retrieved from:

<https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/belgium/reception-conditions/employment-and-education/access-education/>

AIDA/ECRE (2023) Access to Education: Spain. Retrieved from:

<https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/spain/reception-conditions/employment-and-education/access-education/>

Atkinson, M., Lamont, E., Caroline, G., White, R., Kinder, K. (2009). *School Funding: A review of existing models in European and OECD countries*. National Foundation for Educational Research: Berkshire.

Bedmar, L. Vicente, and Veronika Carmen Delgado-Cobano (2014). The Teaching of Religious Education in Public Schools in the Nordic Countries of Europe. *Review of European Studies*, 6: 50–57.

Brücker, H., Ette, A., Grabka, M. M., Kosyakova, Y., Niehues, W., Rother, N., & Tanis, K. (2023). *Ukrainian refugees in Germany: Escape, arrival and everyday life*. Institute for Employment Research, Nuremberg, Germany.

https://www.bib.bund.de/Publikation/2022/pdf/Ukrainian-refugees-in-Germany-Escape-arrival-and-everyday-life.pdf;jsessionid=7FEA62E170B55036CDA73384E5CF012D.intranet261?__blob=publicationFile&v=3

- Conference of European Statisticians Task Force. (2022). *Statistics on children: Spotlight on children exposed to violence, in alternative care, and with disabilities*. New York: United Nations Publications.
- Department of Education (2023) *Department of Education confirms 15,625 Ukrainian pupils enrolled in Irish schools at end of school year 2022 / 2023* <https://www.gov.ie/en/press-release/3410a-department-of-education-confirms-15625-ukrainian-pupils-enrolled-in-irish-schools-at-end-of-school-year-2022-2023/>
- DIW (2023) Weekly Report, 13(28). *Ukrainian refugees: Nearly half intend to stay in Germany for the longer term* https://www.diw.de/documents/publikationen/73/diw_01.c.878219.de/dwr-23-28-1.pdf
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture, (2022). *Supporting the inclusion of displaced children from Ukraine in education: considerations, key principles and practices for the school year 2022-2023*, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2766/310985>
- Eurostat (2016) *Urban Europe — statistics on cities, towns and suburbs — foreign-born persons living in cities*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:Urban_Europe_%E2%80%94_statistics_on_cities,_towns_and_suburbs_%E2%80%94_foreign-born_persons_living_in_cities&oldid=294560#:~:text=The%20four%20largest%20communities%20of,absolute%20number%20of%20foreign%2Dborn
- Eur Lex (2013). Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 *Laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32013L0033>
- European Commission / EACEA / Eurydice, 2022. *Structural indicators for monitoring education and training systems in Europe – 2022: Overview of major reforms since 2015*. Eurydice background report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Fundamental Rights Agency (2019) *Integration of young refugees in the EU: good practices and challenges* https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2019-integration-young-refugees_en.pdf
- Fundamental Rights Agency (2020) *Integrating Young Refugees EU Country Information* <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2020/integrating-young-refugees-eu-country-information#publication-tab-0>
- Heiervang, E. & Goodman, R. (2011). Advantages and limitations of web-based surveys: evidence from a child mental health survey. *Social Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 46, 69–76.
- Horgan, D., Martin, S., O’Riordan, J., & Maier, R. (2022). Supporting languages: The socio-educational integration of migrant and refugee children and young people. *Children & Society*, 36, 369–385. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12525>
- Heidi, B., Miller, A. B., Baldwin, H., & Abdi, S. (2011). New directions in refugee youth mental health services: Overcoming barriers to engagement. *Journal of Child & Adolescent Trauma*, 4, 69-85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361521.2011.545047>
- Jiang, X. & Peguero, A. (2017). Immigration, extracurricular activity, and the role of family. *Education and Urban Society*, 49(3), 314-340.
- Koehler, C., & Schneider, J. (2019). Young refugees in education: The particular challenges of school systems in Europe. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s4087-8-019-0129-3>.

- Landsdown, G. 2011 *Every Child's Right to be Heard. A Resource Guide on the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child General Comment No 12*, Save the Children.
- Lundy, L. and McEvoy, (2012). Childhood, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child and research: What constitutes a rights-based approach? In M. Freeman (ed.), *Law and Childhood* (pp.75-91). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Milkaite, I. & Lievens, E. (2019). *Status quo regarding the child's article 8 GDPR age of consent for data processing across the EU*. Available at: <https://www.betterinternetforkids.eu/practice/articles/article?id=3017751> (Accessed 31 January, 2023).
- Massing, C., Ghadi, N., Kikulwe, D., Nakutnyy, K. (2023). Elementry Schooling Across Borders: Refugee Background Children's Pre- and Post-Migration Experiences, *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 0:0:1-18
- Noorani, S., Baïdak, N., Krémó, A. and Riiheläinen, J. 2019 *Eurydice Brief Integrating Students from Migrant Backgrounds into Schools in Europe: National Policies and Measures*. European Commission.
- Noorani, S., & Antonello, D. (2022). *Supporting refugee learners from Ukraine in schools in Europe*. Eurydice report. European Education and Culture Executive Agency, European Commission.
https://www.uhr.se/globalassets/_uhr.se/internationellt/eurydike/supporting_refugee_learners_from_ukraine_in_schools_in_europe.pdf
- Network for Dialogue (2022) *Ensuring Migrant and Refugee Children's Access to Formal Education in Europe* <https://network4dialogue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Network-for-Dialogue-Policy-Brief-6-Access-to-Formal-Education.pdf>
- OECD (2023). *Education at a Glance 2032: OECD Indicators*, OECD Publishing, Paris.
<https://www.oecd.org/education/education-at-a-glance/>
- OECD/PISA 2018 Results (Volume II): *Where All Students Can Succeed Performance and academic resilience amongst students with an immigrant background*. Retrieved from: https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/pisa-2018-results-volume-ii_263bde74-en#page5
- , T., Episkopou, M., Schillberg, E. Brcanski, J. & Jovic, M.(2016) '*Migrant children in transit: health profile and social needs of unaccompanied and accompanied children visiting the MSF clinic in Belgrade, Serbia*'. *Conflict and Health*. 15(32) p.1-10.
- UNESCO (2017). *The quality factor: Strengthening national data to monitor the sustainable development goals*. Montreal: UNESCO Institute for Statistics.
- UNESCO (2023). *Ukrainian refugees' pathways to inclusion in education: Insights from host countries*. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/ukrainian-refugees-pathways-inclusion-education-insights-host-countries> Accessed 17 August 2023.
- UNESCO (2023, May 10). *Mapping education responses for Ukrainian refugees*.
<https://www.unesco.org/en/ukraine-war/education>
- UNHCR, UNICEF, IOM, (2019). *Access to Education for Refugee and Migrant Children in Europe*. Available at <https://www.unhcr.org/neu/wp-content/uploads/sites/15/2019/09/Access-to-education-europe-19.pdf> Accessed 21 August 2023.
- Van Esveld, B. (2023). A Will and a Way: Making Displaced Children's Rights to Education Enforceable, *Laws*, 12(1),16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws12010016> Accessed 21 August 2023.

9 Appendices

a. Appendix A: IMMERSE questionnaires-

This appendix provides access to the English text for the online IMMERSE questionnaires for younger children (7-9 years old), older children (10-18 years old), principals and teachers.

The questionnaires are available at the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/immerse-h2020>

Questionnaires were made available to sites either online or in pen-and-paper (PAP) format, and it was up to the site which was used. Online questionnaires were accessed via a URL or QR code that brought participants to a webpage where they answered a series of filter questions to direct them to the correct questionnaire for their country, participant type (child/young person, principal or teacher) and age. Skip patterns and other details are noted in the text below.

The PAP questionnaires were largely the same as the online versions with some minor adjustments to accommodate skip patterns that were easily accomplished in the online version but would not have been possible in the PAP versions.

The questionnaires for younger and older children were available in 11 languages in all countries: Dutch, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, Spanish, Arabic, Farsi, Romanian and Chinese. In the late stages of the data collection, the older children's questionnaire only was also translated into Urdu (PAP only), Somali (PAP only), Ukrainian (online only), and Russian (online only) to reach key groups in Greece and Germany who would otherwise have been unable to participate. The questionnaires for principals and teachers were available in English and the majority language of the country.

b. Appendix B: Country sampling overviews and changes

i. Belgium

	Original sampling strategy (July 2020)	Changes to sampling strategy
Regions	<p>Ghent (Flanders) Mechelen (Antwerp) Brussels</p> <p>All districts in all three cities</p>	<p>JANUARY 2022</p> <p>Expanded to most other regions in Flanders and Wallonia (including Antwerp) - expansion into Flanders was successful, resulted in 8 additional sites, expansion into Wallonia had some initial interest but no new sites ultimately participated</p>
Rationale	<p>Flanders was selected because it comprises more than half the Belgian population (majority Dutch speaking). Ghent is the second largest city in Flanders, located in East Flanders. Mechelen is in the Antwerp region and was selected because it is a relatively small city, but with a very high number of children from a migrant background (one in two children born in Mechelen has a migrant background). Brussels was selected because it is the most populous city in Belgium and although officially bilingual is predominantly French speaking, and the French schools fall under the competence of the Wallonia education authority. It is a capital city, has its own government and status, is officially French and Dutch, education is covered by both education ministries in each commune, and it has a high concentration of migrants.</p>	<p>Expanded to areas with reasonably high migrant populations and where we had professional contacts likely to result in successful recruitment</p>
Schools/types of sites	<p>Primary: Official community and official subsidised categories (state-aided)</p> <p>Secondary: schools with OKAN/DASPA (reception education for migrants, usually attached to community organised, community subsidised, or free subsidised schools)</p>	<p>JANUARY 2022:</p> <p>Added Dutch schools in Brussels</p> <p>Added vocational tracts (secondary schools)</p>

	<p>No private education sites No European and international schools No special needs schools</p> <p>Non-formal sites: children and youth centres, community centres, migrant-led self-organised initiatives, NGOs and associations</p>	<p>Added more variety of non-formal environments (after-school groups, language programmes, summer schools - this was especially successful for summer 2022)</p>
<p>Criteria used in sampling frame categories</p>	<p>Region: Mechelen (Dutch speaking), Ghent (Dutch speaking), Brussels (French speaking) School levels: primary, lower secondary, upper secondary</p> <p>No publicly available information at school levels to use for other criteria (e.g. school size, migrant concentration)</p> <p>3 categories for each region: primary, lower secondary (focus on schools with OKAN/DASPA), upper secondary (focus on schools with OKAN/DASPA)</p>	<p>no change</p>
<p>Type of sampling</p>	<p>Stratified random sampling of: Brussels: 10 schools across 3 school levels Ghent: 5 schools across 3 school levels Mechelen: 5 schools across 3 school levels</p> <p>Non-probability sampling of: non-formal sites</p>	<p>JANUARY 2022 Continued to pursue stratified sampling but no longer randomly, contacted all schools in all categories to expedite and boost recruitment</p> <p>Started to pursue (in tandem) non-probability sampling using professional networks and contacts, snowball recruitment</p> <p>MAY/JUNE 2022 Re-contacted all OKAN/DASPA schools for fall participation</p>
<p>Classes</p>	<p>Primary: All classes, all years</p> <p>Secondary:</p>	<p>MAY 2022 As many as site would agree to</p>

	All classes, all years	
Consent approach	<p>School-based consent for all children in schools (active individual parent consent not needed), schools still in some cases sending opt-out to parents to inform them of study and GDPR considerations</p> <p>In non-formal environments, children under 13 require active individual parent consent</p>	No change needed

While every school was approached with a request to survey whole classes and full year groups, researchers ultimately had to accommodate what the site would allow. This sometimes meant collecting data from only certain classes, year groups or groups of students. The following sites in Belgium restricted data collection to certain years/groups of students:

Site	Groups surveyed
6205	only derde leerjaar (2de graad) ASO/ 3ème secondaire général (G) and vierde leerjaar (2de graad) BSO/TSO/ 4ème secondaire technique (T) / professionnel (P)
6232	only vijfde leerjaar/ 5ème primaire
6306	only OKAN/DASPA
6308	only OKAN/DASPA
6310	only OKAN/DASPA
6403	only lower secondary
6409	only vierde leerjaar/ 4ème primaire and vijfde leerjaar/ 5ème primaire

ii. Germany

	Original sampling strategy (July 2020)	Changes to sampling strategy
Regions	Leipzig (Saxony) Berlin (Berlin)	APRIL 2022

	<p>Cologne (North Rhine-Westphalia)</p>	<p>Expanded to Lörrach (Baden Württemberg), result of networking at an Erasmus+ event</p> <p>MAY 2022 Expanded within North Rhine-Westphalia to 6 additional cities (Wuppertal, Dortmund, Hagen, Gelsenkirchen, Bielefeld, and Duisburg)</p> <p>SEPTEMBER 2022 Expansion to Dresden and Rheinland Palatine</p> <p>2023 Expansion to Saxony-Anhalt, Baden-Württemberg (vocational schools), spreading all across Saxony (Zittau, Chemnitz, Görlitz, Borna, Löbau, Bautzen, Zwickau, Hoyerswerda, Bischofswerda, Radeberg and Kamenz)</p>
<p>Rationale</p>	<p>The regional selection was following the rationale of the varying degrees of distribution of the population with migration background and experience in dealing with migration in an educational context. Therefore, the three cities were selected accordingly. Leipzig is the biggest city in Saxony and was selected as the East German representative. Berlin is the biggest city of Germany, its capital, and presents a very diverse environment due to its divided history. Cologne is the most populated city in North Rhine-Westphalia and is an example of high experience with migration and educational integration.</p>	<p>Expanded to areas with reasonably high migrant populations and with professional networks that could facilitate successful recruitment.</p>
<p>Schools/types of sites</p>	<p>Public (state-aided), general education No entirely private schools No European and international schools No special needs schools</p>	<p>MARCH 2022 Informal centres - afterschool programmes, family cohorts from migrant community</p>

	<p>Non-formal sites: children and youth centres, community centres, migrant-led self-organised initiatives, NGOs and association</p>	<p>JUNE 2022 Vocational schools added, resulted in new sites in NRW and Baden Württemberg Informal centres - home language informal learning group</p>
<p>Criteria used in sampling frame categories</p>	<p>School type: primary schools, middle schools, secondary schools, joint schools (some combination of primary, middle, secondary) School type varies by state.</p> <p>Size: number of students, small (<300), medium (300-599), and large (600+)</p> <p>Proportion of students with migrant background: for Berlin this is measured by school, for Leipzig and Cologne this is measured by the district the school is in because school-level data on this indicator is not publicly available</p> <p>Berlin: share of students in the school with migrant background, low (<30%), medium (30-60%), and high (60%+)</p> <p>Leipzig and Cologne: share of population in the school's district with migrant background, for Cologne, low (<30%), medium (30-50%), and high (50%+), for Leipzig low (<10%), medium (10-20%), and high (20%+)</p> <p>School levels: primary, lower secondary, upper secondary</p>	<p>no change</p>
<p>Type of sampling</p>	<p>Stratified random sampling of: Schools in each category of sampling frame. Proportional to number of schools in each region (i.e. more schools/pupils from Berlin because it is far more populous than Leipzig or Cologne).</p> <p>Non-probability sampling of: non-formal education environments</p>	<p>MARCH 2022 Started to pursue (in tandem with continued random sampling) non-probability sampling using professional networks and contacts, snowball recruitment</p>

Classes	All classes, all year groups if possible	No change, as much as site would agree to
Consent approach	<p>In schools, active individual consent for those 13 and under from parent/guardian. Those 14 years and older can consent for themselves (following GDPR legislation).</p> <p>In non-formal centres, those 17 and under need active individual consent from parent/guardian.</p>	<p>MARCH 2022</p> <p>Investigation showed regulations around consent vary from region to region and even school to school. Approach used was whatever the site would allow that will yield maximum numbers - school-based, opt out, active opt in.</p>

While every school was approached with a request to survey whole classes and full year groups, researchers ultimately had to accommodate what the site would allow. This sometimes meant collecting data from only certain classes, year groups or groups of students. In the end, all schools set restrictions on the students we could survey, e.g. only the classes whose teachers agreed, 2nd/3rd grade onwards, only up to 7th/8th grade, only migrants selected by the school itself, etc.

iii. Greece

	Original sampling strategy (July 2020)	Changes to sampling strategy
Regions	<p>Attica</p> <p>Central Macedonia</p> <p>Crete</p> <p>Thessaly</p> <p>Epirus</p> <p>Eastern Macedonia (first line for reception of asylum seekers)</p> <p>North Aegean Islands (first line for reception of asylum seekers)</p> <p>These 7 regions cover 3 main axes of geographical difference (mainland vs islands, north vs south, central vs bordering neighbouring countries)</p>	<p>APRIL 2022</p> <p>RDPSEC (Crete): Expanding to more cities and town on Crete</p> <p>Panteion: Expanding to more cities and towns in Greece within original sampling regions and to other areas: Euboea (Central Greece – 1 new site), Achaia (Northern Peloponnese – 1 new site), and Thrace (Northeastern Greece – 2 new sites)</p>

<p>Rationale</p>	<p>The total number of foreign born persons present in Greece cannot be calculated with accuracy mostly because of the lack of a unified recording system on migrants and refugees by a national/ European/ international authority and also due to the high and constant mobility of the migrant and refugee population both within the country and of people passing through the country towards another European country. However, we have compiled what data is available in order to choose regions that represent important axes of geographical difference and where migrant and refugee populations are concentrated in order to be able to collect the requisite amount of data.</p>	<p>Expanded to areas with reasonably high migrant populations and where we had professional contacts likely to result in successful recruitment</p>
<p>Schools/types of sites</p>	<p>"Plain" schools - no special supports for migrant/EAL students, no particular emphasis on integration or interculturalism</p> <p>DYEP - schools with preparatory classes for asylum seekers ZEP - special lessons for non-Greek speakers in core subjects Intercultural - schools with special emphasis on intercultural communication, diversity of culture and language</p> <p>1 private education site</p> <p>No European and international schools No special needs schools</p> <p>Non-formal sites: Open reception facilities (ORFs), ORFs with "Safe Zones" for UAMs</p>	<p>APRIL 2022 UASC shelters for UAMs</p> <p>MAY 2022 (Crete): vocational upper secondary schools added</p> <p>JUNE 2022 (Crete): attempting to recruit refugees from shelter for UAMs (ultimately did not participate) Received official permission for data collection in UASC shelters in Athens, Lesbos and Chios</p>
<p>Criteria used in sampling frame categories</p>	<p>School level: primary, lower secondary, upper secondary</p> <p>School types based on supports for migrants & refugees: "plain", DYEP, ZEP, intercultural</p>	<p>no change</p>

	<p>No publicly available information at school levels to use for other criteria (e.g. size)</p> <p>Resulted in 7 categories for each level in each region, to reach schools in all categories that apply in each region</p> <p>Total of 60 schools</p>	
<p>Type of sampling</p>	<p>Stratified random sampling of: Schools in each category of sampling frame from a comprehensive list</p> <p>Non-probability sampling of: Back-up plan for schools - targeted short list of 200 schools likely to respond positively</p> <p>Non-formal sites using networks and contacts</p>	<p>APRIL 2022</p> <p>Started to pursue (in tandem with continued random sampling) non-probability sampling using professional networks and contacts, snowball recruitment</p>
<p>Classes</p>	<p>Primary: All classes, all year groups with target of approximately 40 students/school, minimum of 20% migrant/refugee background in classes unless there are DYEP/ZEP classes present in which case those would be chosen automatically</p> <p>Secondary: All classes, all year groups with target of approximately 40 students/school, minimum of 20% migrant/refugee background in classes unless there are DYEP/ZEP classes present in which case those would be chosen automatically</p>	<p>MARCH 2022 (Panteion) As many classes, year groups as schools will allow</p> <p>MAY 2022 (RDPSEC) Focusing on classes with highest migrant concentrations given imperative of hitting target and 2 hour time constraint</p>

	(Crete): all classes, all years, as much as can be accomplished within 2 hour window that schools have imposed	
Consent approach	<p>Active individual consent required from parents/ guardians if children are under 18 years old</p> <p>Those 18 years and older can consent for themselves</p> <p>In non-formal environments in the case of UAMs, official authorization provided by the legal Prosecutor having the area of responsibility of each UAM shelter.</p>	<p>(Crete): change in consent approach not an option, per educational authorities on Crete, continued with active individual consent from parents for those under 18</p> <p>JUNE 2022</p> <p>Panteion: opt-out approach was not thought to be an option, but further investigation and inquiry ascertained that this was not the case for schools. Consent in schools switched to opt-out from September 2022. Consent for UAMs in shelters continued using established procedure with relevant authorities.</p>

No schools in Greece restricted data collection to specific classes, year groups, or groups of students, however the pursuit of active individual consent from parents resulted in low numbers in some sites, as parent engagement and trust was often difficult to gain.

iv. Ireland

	Original sampling strategy (July 2020)	Changes to sampling strategy
Regions	Dublin Limerick Cork	MARCH 2022 Added Waterford (gained 3 schools as a result) Expanded Limerick to entire metropolitan area (gained 1 school as a result)
Rationale	According to 2016 census data (the most recent census), Ireland’s migrant population is highly concentrated in urban areas, in particular the city centres of Dublin, Cork, and Limerick, and the suburbs of West and North Dublin. These areas account for about half of the country’s migrants and contain electoral districts (EDs) that have as much as 59% foreign-born residents. Most rural areas,	Expanded to areas with reasonably high migrant populations and where we had professional contacts likely to result in successful recruitment

	<p>by contrast, have less than 5% foreign-born residents, with 81 EDs having only one or no foreign-born residents. Due to practical and financial constraints related to personnel, travel, and ensuring our participant quota, we have therefore decided to concentrate on Dublin, Cork, and Limerick as our data collection regions.</p>	
<p>Schools/types of sites</p>	<p>State-aided (no private) Mainstream (no special-needs-only schools) English medium (no Irish medium) 120 or more pupils (to ensure big enough classes) No European and international schools</p>	<p>MARCH 2022: Added Youth Reach centres to capture early school leavers (2 in Dublin, 1 in Cork participated)</p> <p>Directly targeted schools with vocational tracks (they were part of original sample but had not come up in random sampling, yet)</p>
<p>Criteria used in sampling frame categories</p>	<p>School size: small (120-400 pupils) or large (401+) Religious affiliation: yes (Catholic/Church of Ireland) or no (multi-denominational) DEIS status: proxy for SES, DEIS or non-DEIS no information available on migrant concentration at school level 3 binary criteria resulted in 8 categories</p>	<p>no change</p>
<p>Type of sampling</p>	<p>Stratified random sampling of: Dublin: at least one school in each category at primary and secondary level (16 schools altogether) Cork: at least one school in each viable category (not all categories had schools that met criteria) and 2 from DEIS categories (12 schools altogether) Limerick: at least one school in each viable category (not all categories had schools that met criteria) and 2 from DEIS categories (10 schools altogether)</p> <p>Direct targeting of:</p>	<p>MARCH 2022 Continued to pursue stratified sampling but no longer randomly, contacted all schools in all categories to expedite and boost recruitment</p> <p>Started to pursue (in tandem) non-probability sampling using professional networks and contacts, snowball recruitment</p>

	<p>schools near Direct Provision centres to ensure some asylum-seeking children in sample</p>	
<p>Classes</p>	<p>Primary: Alternate years - 1st/3rd/5th class (changed to 2nd/4th/6th class after 6-year-olds were dropped from study) random sampling of classes if more than 2 in a year group</p> <p>Secondary: Alternate years - 1st/3rd/5th year random sampling of classes if more than 2 in a year group</p>	<p>MARCH 2022</p> <p>When recruiting asked for all year groups and classes possible, went with as much as school would allow, can see the expansion in sites from May/June 2022 on</p>
<p>Consent approach</p>	<p>Active opt-in consent for all children in schools, gathered through the IMMERSE landing page</p> <p>Participant own consent only for those 18 in non-formal environments</p>	<p>NOVEMBER 2021</p> <p>Used school communication platform to gather consents from parents, more efficient and higher numbers of consents, however it did mean no chance to collect parent data. As time went on and it became clear that parent data would likely be dropped from the study (around April/May 2022), we used this method more and more and even offered it to schools as an option for collecting consents (first offered in April 2022).</p> <p>APRIL 2022</p> <p>Tried to amend ethics approval to move to an opt-out approach to boost numbers, but this was rejected by the ethics board.</p>

While every school was approached with a request to survey whole classes and full year groups, researchers ultimately had to accommodate what the site would allow. This sometimes meant collecting data from only certain classes, year groups or groups of students. The following sites in Ireland restricted data collection to certain years/groups of students:

Site	Groups surveyed
2203	5 th years only
2165	1 st /2 nd /3 rd years only

2286	4 th /5 th years only
2470	2 nd years only
2385	1 st /2 nd years only
2143	2 nd /3 rd class only
2131	3 rd class only
2309	Migrant background students only

v. Italy

	Original sampling strategy (July 2020)	Changes to sampling strategy
Regions	<p>Milan (Lombardy - north) Turin (Piedmont - north) Rome (Lazio - central) Naples (Campania - south) Catania (Sicily - islands)</p>	<p>OCTOBER 2022 Expanded to: Mestre (Veneto - north) Marghera (Veneto - north) Prato (Tuscany - central) Bari (Puglia - south) Scalea (Calabria - south)</p>
Rationale	<p>The cities are good representatives of the regions they are part of. The selection of the regions also follows the criterion of geographical, social, cultural and economic heterogeneity of the population surveyed. Socio-economic status is much higher in the north of the Country compared to the centre and especially compared to the south and the islands. The distribution of migrants and foreign students in the areas is very different, with higher rates in the centre-north than in the south. The south and the islands, however, are the areas where the challenge of first reception of migrants coming through the Mediterranean path has been faced in recent decades, although their routes then mostly move to other areas of the country. In the five cities, the</p>	<p>Expanded to territories where SCIT has school projects and informal educational centres</p>

	<p>sampling will cover only the urban areas; however, different districts and zones will be involved, with the aim of recovering a certain variety internal to the city contexts.</p>	
Schools/types of sites	<p>State-aided (no private education sites) in the top three quartiles in terms of number of pupils (smallest schools excluded)</p> <p>No European and international schools No special needs schools</p> <p>Non-formal sites: informal educational centres, after-school support, day care centres for marginalised minors (all nationalities).</p>	<p>JANUARY 2022 sampling extended to vocational tracts in schools</p> <p>JUNE 2022 Identification of more non-formal centres (youth centres, after-school classes, language programmes, summer schools) 7 new centres identified to be included in November data collection</p>
Criteria used in sampling frame categories	<p>Comprehensive school lists compiled for each of the 5 cities and then divided by:</p> <p>School level: primary, lower secondary, upper secondary</p> <p>Results in 15 categories. School lists were narrowed by: School size: schools in the lowest quartile for number of pupils are excluded Share of migrant pupils: schools in the lowest quartile for proportion of migrant pupils excluded (thresholds identified at the city level as concentration of migrants varies by location)</p> <p>Attempts will be made to reach 4 schools in each category for a total of 60 schools.</p>	<p>no change</p>
Type of sampling	<p>Stratified weighted random sampling of: Schools in each category of sampling frame. Weighted random sampling means a random extraction weighed for the estimation of foreign students in that school, so all eligible schools could be</p>	<p>APRIL 2022 Started to pursue (in tandem with continued random sampling) non-probability sampling using professional networks and contacts, snowball recruitment</p>

	<p>extracted but the ones with higher proportions of foreign students have a greater chance.</p> <p>Non-probability sampling of: Non-formal sites using networks and contacts with educational centres that are part of the SCI local networks, will attempt to reach approximately the same amount of children in each city</p>	<p>MAY/JUNE 2022</p> <p>Reviewed original contact lists to find schools who were interested but did not have time/resources to participate in 21/22 academic year to try to recruit for fall</p>
Classes	<p>All classes, all year groups if possible</p> <p>If school restricts number of classes/year groups, they will be selected randomly.</p>	<p>No change</p>
Consent approach	<p>Active individual consent required from parents/ guardians if children are under 18 years old (consent forms modified so one parent can indicate consent for second guardian if applicable)</p> <p>Those 18 years and older can consent for themselves</p> <p>In non-formal environments in the case of UAMs, consent will be sought from appropriate guardian if participant is under 18</p>	<p>MAY 2022</p> <p>Confirmation that school-based consent could replace active individual consent in schools, in place from September 2022 on</p>

While every school was approached with a request to survey whole classes and full year groups, researchers ultimately had to accommodate what the site would allow. This sometimes meant collecting data from only certain classes, year groups or groups of students. The following sites in Italy restricted data collection to certain years/groups of students:

Site	Groups surveyed
3658	Students with migrant background only (already part of a regional project)
3659	Students with migrant background only (already part of a regional project)

vi. Spain

	Original sampling strategy (July 2020)	Changes to sampling strategy
Regions	<p>Madrid (province) La Rioja (province) Malaga (province) Almeria (province) Huelva (province)</p> <p>Census sections in each province with a share of foreign-born residents that was 20% or lower were excluded.</p>	<p>MAY 2021 Malaga, Almeria and Huelva dropped after not getting authorization from the Andalusian authorities to survey their Autonomous Community.</p> <p>SEPTEMBER 2021 Expanded to Alicante, Castellon, Valencia</p> <p>FEBRUARY 2022 Expanded to more centres in existing sample areas</p> <p>MARCH 2022 Expanded to specific areas where sites known to be willing to participate were located (Albacete, Lorca-Murcia, Lleida, Cuenca, Toledo, Cantabria, Balearic Islands, Salamanca)</p> <p>JANUARY 2023 Expanded to specific areas where sites known to be willing to participate were located (Seville, Cordoba, Almeria, Granada, Cadiz)</p>
Rationale	<p>The regions or Autonomous Communities selected to carry out the IMMERSE survey in Spain are three: The Community of Madrid (hereinafter, Madrid), Andalusia and La Rioja. Considering the provincial division of the Spanish territory and, above all, based on the geographic size of Andalusia, which is the second largest Autonomous Community of the State, our unit of measurement</p>	<p>Expanded to areas with reasonably high migrant populations and where we would be able to get permission from authorities and had professional contacts likely to result in successful recruitment</p>

	<p>will be the province. Madrid and La Rioja are single province regions, but in Andalusia the fieldwork will be done in Malaga, Almeria and Huelva because these are the provinces having the largest share of migrant population in this Community. Therefore, the fieldwork will be carried out in five provinces, all selected according to territorial dispersion, rural/urban variability and percentage of foreign population and foreign students in relation to the total student body.</p>	
<p>Schools/types of sites</p>	<p>Public and private subsidised with public funds, entirely private schools excluded</p> <p>No European and international schools No special needs schools</p> <p>Non-formal sites: In Spain, the vast majority of children somehow attend formal educational environments. Consequently, there is a lack of systematised data on the characteristics of key non-formal education environments for migrants in Spain, which in turn present higher levels of inaccessibility. For this reason, we will not include non-formal education centres in our sampling strategy (leaving them for the case studies).</p>	<p>MARCH 2022 Recruiting centres for UAMs</p> <p>JANUARY 2023 More centres for UAMs</p>
<p>Criteria used in sampling frame categories</p>	<p>Comprehensive school lists compiled for each of the provinces and then divided by:</p> <p>Ownership: public and subsidised private</p> <p>School level: primary, secondary/high school, basic professional training/vocational education and training</p> <p>Proportion of foreign students: percentage of school population that was born abroad (minimum 15%)</p> <p>Size: small (fewer than 300), medium (300-450), large (450+)</p> <p>Urban/rural: fewer than 30,000 inhabitants</p> <p>Household income: low/medium/high according to income deciles</p>	<p>no change</p> <p>Added UAM reception centres where we had access</p>

<p>Type of sampling</p>	<p>Stratified random sampling of: Schools in each category of sampling frame. Proportional to share of foreign-born students in each province with a minimum of 5 centres per province, proportional to share of public/subsidised private, urban/rural, small/med/large</p>	<p>MARCH 2022 UAMs centers where qualitative fieldwork was carried out were contacted by the team to request them filling the survey. In the case of Castilla La Mancha region, in addition to the public reception center of Albacete, the NGO DIAGRAMA had other 3 centres, these were contacted to the intermediation of the Department of Social Welfare of Castilla la Mancha that authorized us to carry out the survey there.</p> <p>APRIL 2022 Started to pursue (in tandem with continued random sampling) non-probability sampling of schools using professional networks and contacts, snowball recruitment</p> <p>JANUARY - MAY 2023 Through networking of the University Institute of Studies on Migration we came across an NGO called SAMU which worked with UAMs in Andalusia region. They provided the links to those who were 18 years old (one site) in Janaury, and the possibility to collect data with children under 18 if we got the permission of the Junta de Andalucía. Once we received it in May, we conducted data collection in 12 centres hosting UAMs.</p>
<p>Classes</p>	<p>All classes, all year groups if possible</p>	<p>No change</p>
<p>Consent approach</p>	<p>School-based consent for those 13 and under Those 14 years and older can consent for themselves (following GDPR legislation)</p>	<p>No change needed</p>